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THE EFFECTS OF INTERPERSONAL AND ECONOMIC
RESOURCES UPON VALUES AND THE QUALITY OF LIFE

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TABLES

	page
Table 1. Subject Population Characteristics . . .	37
Table 2. REVIR Mean Scores for College Students	44
Table 3. Correlations of Each Area with the Over-all Total Score for Each Scale for the REVIR IV Test	52
Table 4. Correlations of Each Area with the Over-all Total Score for Each Scale for the REVIR V Test	52
Table 5. Intercorrelations of the REVIR IV Scales	54
Table 6. REVIR IV Test - Retest (2 Weeks) Correlations	56
Table 7. Correlations Between the REVIR IV and the Marlowe-Crowne (S-D) Scale	59
Table 8. Significant Correlations Between the REVIR IV and the FIRO-B	69
Table 9. Values and Vocational Choices	72
Table 10. The Correlations Between Volunteering for Encounter Workshops and Values	75
Table 11. Correlations Between the Availability of an Intimate Other and Current Resource Income	82
Table 12. Correlations Between Receiving Resources Currently and One's General State of Happiness	85
Table 13. Step-Wise Regression of Current Resources Received and One's General State of Happiness	87

Table 14.	ANOV Summary Results of the Effects of Love and Money Incomes Upon Happiness	89
Table 15.	ANOV Summary Results of the Effects of Love and Money Incomes in Childhood Upon Current Values	94
Table 16.	The Effects of Love and Money Incomes in Childhood Upon the Current Value of Money - Cell Means and Simple Effects .	95
Table 17.	The Effects of Love and Money Incomes in Childhood Upon the Current Value of Love - Cell Means and Simple Effects .	100
Table 18.	ANOV Summary Results of the Effects of Love and Money Incomes Currently Upon Values	103

FIGURES

	page
Figure 1. The Arrangement of Resources According to the Dimensions of Particularism and Concreteness	3
Figure 2. The Effects of Love and Money Upon One's General State of Happiness	90
Figure 3. The Effects of Love and Money Upon One's General State of Happiness - Interactions.	93
Figure 4. The Effects of Love and Money Incomes in Childhood Upon the Value of Money.	.98
Figure 5. The Effects of Love and Money Incomes in Childhood Upon the Value of Love .	101
Figure 6. The Effects of Current Love and Money Incomes Upon the Value of Goods . . .	.104

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Resources, Values and the Quality of Life

The quality of life may not only be a function of the scarcity or accessibility of interpersonal or economic resources, but may also be a function of an individual's own priorities in life or values. A simple paradigm is suggested, i.e., that the long-term exchange of resources leads to the formation of a relatively enduring evaluation of resources. These resource values affect our motivation to choose or seek various resources, and the long-term acquisition of resources is related to one's general degree of happiness or quality of life. This paradigm becomes illustrative of a maladaptive system when the past exchange of resources leads to the formation of substitute or compensatory resource values that are unrelated to the individual's actual needs or deficiencies, and that orients him towards resources that are less related to happiness.

Foa's (1971; Foa & Foa, 1974) resource exchange theory serves as the theoretical basis for the variables of this research. Foa's resource exchange theory specifies six main resources which can be exchanged in interpersonal situations. They are love (warmth, affection); status (respect, esteem); information (advice, knowledge); money (coin, currency); goods (material commodities); and services (work, labor). The six resources form a circle when arranged

along two axes: the vertical axis representing the particular - universal dimension and the horizontal axis representing the symbolic - concrete dimension (see fig. 1). Specific predictions may be made concerning immediate interpersonal exchanges.

For example, neighboring resources are the most acceptable exchanges. Money and goods, as neighboring resources, are easily exchangeable. Also love and status are neighboring resources; and if love cannot be exchanged for love, giving status is a more acceptable exchange for love than would be money (money is the most distant resource from love).

Love is the most particularistic resource, and money is the most universal resource. So while it matters very little with whom we may exchange money, we do not exchange love with just anyone. Goods and services are the most concrete resources, while status and information are the most symbolic resources. Love and money represent the middle position on this dimension, as love and money have both concrete and symbolic components.

B. Resources and Happiness

This research centers primarily on the particularism dimension and the resources of love and money. The acquisition of resources is expected to be related to an individual's quality of life, or general state of happiness. However,

FIG. I. THE ARRANGEMENT OF RESOURCES
ACCORDING TO THE DIMENSIONS OF
PARTICULARISM AND CONCRETENESS

it is also expected that there are qualitative differences among the resources along the particularism dimension in their relationship to happiness. That is, the more particular the resource, the greater the relationship between acquiring it and happiness.

1. Money and Happiness

Economic resources have been significantly related to the quality of life. Money provides the means by which individuals in society obtain basic survival needs such as food, clothing, and shelter. Cantril (1965) was able to relate the concerns of people from several nations to various social and economic indicators. He used a visual scale called the "ladder of life," which constituted a self-defined continuum. The bottom of the ladder represented "the worst possible life" (a score of one) and the top of the ladder represented "the best possible life" (a score of ten). The ladder scale was administered to a cross-section of the adult population of thirteen countries. The gross national product of the countries was found to be highly related to their inhabitants' rating of their quality of life.

Bradburn's (1963) research further illustrates the importance of money to the quality of life in America. Whereas Cantril's data were cross-cultural, Bradburn's study was intra-cultural comparing four towns in Illinois.

One town was consistently prosperous, another had shown recent economic progress, and the other two towns were economically depressed.

He found the quality of life of the people from these various towns to be related to such factors as income, age, education, and marital status:

(a) the percentage of "not too happy" was greatest for the lowest income group and lowest for the highest income group; (b) the percentage of "not too happy" increased with age; (c) the percentage of "not too happy" was greatest for the least educated; and (d) the percentage of "not too happy" was highest for the widowed, next highest for the divorced or separated, lower for the single, and lowest for the married.

Bradburn's results not only indicate that money is related to happiness, but also that non-economic indicators such as marital status are related to happiness. For example, the widowed (who have lost a loved one) were most unhappy, while the married were found to be most happy. Cantril's (1965) data also suggest that non-economic resources may be related to the quality of life. For example, the highest average rating Cantril obtained in his worldwide survey was found for the Israeli Kibbutzim (7.0), higher than that of the monetarily richer United States (6.6) with a yearly per capita income for 1959 of

\$2160. The average national rating for Israel as a whole was only 5.3 (yearly per capita income for 1965 of \$1325). Israeli Kibbutzim are characterized by a highly equalitarian and democratic spirit, a sense of community, and of brotherhood.

Although both Cantril's (1965) cross-cultural study and Bradburn's (1963) American survey show support for the importance of non-economic resources to the quality of life in addition to the monetary resources, neither study is able to adequately measure the non-economic resources so that they may be compared with economic resources to determine the relative contributions of each to personal happiness. There is a possible self-selection which may have inflated the Kibbutzim results in Cantril's research, and marriage does involve the exchange of many resources other than love; so that even if relative differences in love income could be inferred by these categories, they do not provide the continuous scaling necessary to compare the effects of love income with the effects of money income. More importantly, we do not know to what extent each may contribute to the quality of life.

The relationship between money and happiness often appears in research reports, with regard to either specifying how much money contributed to happiness or how much

money contributed to happiness as compared to other non-economic resources. For example, on the cover of the August 1974 issue of Psychology Today were the words: "Not happy? Try money!" They referred to an article by Paul Cameron concerning his research on happiness. The editors preface the article with: "We know money talks, and our research suggests it also makes us happy. Apparently affluence is one of the few things that generally improves life satisfaction..." (p. 64) Cameron did find money to be significantly related to happiness and also: "Physical wholeness, mental capacity, and age seem to have little effect on reported happiness." (p. 64) The conclusion that money "is one of the few things that generally improves life satisfaction" is hardly warranted when money was compared with rather dubious competitors.

The problem lies not only in finding comparable scaling methods, but also in ascertaining which variables are worthwhile to compare. These variables should not be arbitrarily chosen. Theoretically based variables would eliminate random empiricism and would perhaps help to contribute to greater understanding of findings. Foa's (1971; Foa & Foa, 1974) theory of interpersonal resources lends itself to such criteria. The variables or resources are clearly specified and comparison of the variables would be theoretically based.

The relative contributing effects of money to the quality of life could then be compared to the relative contributing effects of the other variables, or resources, such as love, status, information, goods, and services. These are all exchangeable interpersonal resources which can be studied and reasonably researched within Foa's theoretical framework. In Foa's model, money and love are opposite resources. Love is more difficult to scale than would be money, but love income should be considered in its relationship to the quality of life as it may be much more related to the quality of life than is money.

2. Love and Happiness

Many humanitarians claim that love is our most potent resource and that it contributes most to the quality of life, producing the greatest experience of human happiness. The importance of love may be inferred from clinical studies and observations of the effects of love deprivation, or the ambivalence and conditional aspects of the exchange of love during childhood (Berne, 1964; Boatman, 1960; Bowlby, 1965; Freud, 1963; Fromm, 1958; Goldfarb, 1961; Harlow, 1958; Hilgard & Newman, 1963; Lidz & Lidz, 1949; Reich, 1949; Rogers, 1959, 1961; Spitz, 1946). The effects of love can also be inferred from the Cantril (1965) and Bradburn (1963) studies, but

with a good deal of caution. Other studies have shown love to be related to happiness in various ways: marital status, relationships with friends, family members, and in the work situation. Marital status and intimate relationships have shown the most consistent results - indicating that marriage, particularly a happy marriage, is highly related to general life satisfaction (Bradburn, 1963; Gurin et al., 1960; Veroff et al., 1962; Washburne, 1941; Watson, 1930; Wessman & Ricks, 1956).

Veroff et al. (1962) found that marital happiness correlated more highly with happiness than did any other variable (twenty-two for men and nineteen for women). With a sample of 255 married men, the correlation for marital happiness was .38 (beyond the .001 level of significance). The next highest correlates beyond the .001 level of significance were: psychosomatic problems (-.24), problems with children (-.20). With a sample of 542 married women, the highest correlation was marital unhappiness (-.44), then: marital problems (-.24), psychological anxiety (-.19). Other indicators of love income have also been related to happiness - besides those of marital status and adjustment. Sociability, warmth, as well as optimism, emotional stability, and self-insight were found to be related to happiness (Smith, 1961).

Wilson (1960) found that the variables correlated with happiness beyond the .001 level of significance were self-ideal congruency (.47), social adjustment (.41), actual vs. desired achievement discrepancy (-.40), family adjustment (.38), health (.25), dissatisfaction with one's life style (.35), and the person's estimate of his parents' happiness (.28). Wilson did not find significant correlates between happiness and grades, need for achievement, or family income.

Wessman and Ricks (1966) summarized their findings on the happy vs. the unhappy male student: The happy student, as compared with the unhappy student, is a well-adjusted social extravert, able to find satisfaction in work and in interpersonal relations, optimistic, with high self-esteem, confident in being able to achieve his goals, successful, high in ego strength and sense of identity, future oriented, accustomed to success in encounters with the environment from an early age, and from a warm supportive home where he was able to identify with respected and approachable role models. These results not only emphasize the importance of non-economic resources to happiness, but also the importance of having received resources such as love and status in childhood.

Watson (1930) had concluded from his research that a happy home, good relationships with other people including

chronic deprivation of love seems to lead to a devaluation of love, while temporary deprivation of love seems to lead to an increase in the value of love. Chronic deprivation early in life may come to affect our learning to exchange resources and our expectations concerning ourselves and others.

A person who had experienced love poverty may have developed a poor self image or self-esteem. The receiving of warmth or affection may evoke dissonance, anxiety, and suspicion in such an individual (Aronson, 1968, 1972; Rogers, 1959). For example, if in childhood, I had received very little warmth and affection and had not had the opportunity to learn to be intimate, I may have learned to feel unworthy of love or that others are unlikely to be effectively loving. This long-term deprivation of love may lead to a devaluation of love relative to the values of the other resources - these other resources being less related to intimacy and therefore, to anxiety.

However, if I am temporarily alone, I may eventually wish to seek the company of others. This short-term deprivation of love would follow the hunger model of valuation of resources. Just as qualitative differences are expected among the various resources in their

spouse, high job morale, and good health were related to happiness; and that wealth and education of parents, intelligence, and school success were not at all related to happiness. Wilson (1967) concluded his extensive review of the literature on the correlates of avowed happiness with: "Perhaps the most impressive single finding lies in the relationship between happiness and successful involvement with people." (p. 304)

Those resources which a person chooses to seek or orient his life towards are less likely to be based on any empirical relationship between the resources and happiness, but are more likely based on what a person believes will make him happy. These beliefs constitute the individual's subjective value of resources. An individual's resource incomes are not only likely to affect his quality of life, but long-term resource incomes are likely to affect one's value of resources as well.

C. Resources and Values

Values, as discussed in this research, refer to the valuing of a general class of resources. For example, the value of love, as used here, would refer to the general tendency to seek friendship, warmth, and intimacy. Allport (1961) defines values as a form of belief: "A belief upon which man acts by preference." (p. 454) Rokeach (1968, 1973) also defines values as beliefs, especially concerning

specific behavior or goals:

...a value is an enduring belief that a specific mode of conduct or end-state of existence is personally or socially preferable to an opposite or converse mode of conduct or end-state of existence. A value system is an enduring organization of beliefs concerning preferable modes of conduct or end-states of existence along a continuum of relative importance. (p. 5, 1973)

This approach postulates values as enduring cognitive structures formed early in life and functioning without significant effects from recent deprivation or satiation, as opposed to the incentive point of view. Values may remain what Allport (1937) has called "functionally autonomous."

Jones and Gerard (1937) state that values are more basic than attitudes and that they are learned earlier in life than attitudes:

...attitudes are essentially values derived from other values that are more basic or were internalized at an earlier point in development. (p. 707)
...the more important ones are internalized so that they no longer need reinforcement or justification. (p. 159)

Homans' (1958, 1961) social exchange theory defines values according to the behavioral hunger model, whereby value increases as a function of recent deprivation and decreases as a function of recent satiation:

In particular, we must suppose that, with men as with pigeons, an increase in extinction, satiation, or aversive stimulation of any one kind of behavior

will increase the probability of emission of some other kind of behavior. The problem is not, as it is often stated, merely, what man's values are, what he has learned in the past to find reinforcing, but how much of any one value his behavior is getting him now. The more he gets, the less valuable any further unit of that value is to him, and the less often he will emit behavior reinforced by it. (p. 599, 1958)

Since enduring cognitions are not postulated, the effects of the need states must have their effects on values as a recent event: "...the more often a man has in the recent past received a rewarding activity from another, the less valuable any further unit of that activity becomes to him." (p. 55, 1961) It may be that Homans' theory is applicable to short-term exchanges concerning specific objects or resources in a particular situation, as opposed to enduring cognitive beliefs about a general class of resources.

1. Money Deprivation and the Value of Money

There are few laboratory experiments concerning the effects of long-term money deprivation upon the value of money. Bruner and Goodman (1947) found that, unlike rich children, the poor overestimated the perceived size of coins. Although a relationship between the value of money, as measured by perceived coin size, and financial income level was shown, experimental manipulation of long-term deprivation of money was not feasible.

Ashley, Harper and Runyon (1953) replicated the

Bruner and Goodman study, getting similar results while manipulating economic states via hypnotic induction. Although Ashley et al. used hypnotic induction as a way to improve Bruner and Goodman's methodology, the use of hypnosis has its own methodological problems (Rosenthal & Rosnow, 1969).

Furthermore, there has been no consistent use of a standardized scale to measure the relative value of money. Rokeach's (1973) scale of terminal values includes the value "a comfortable life (a prosperous life)." Using Rokeach's value survey, the National Opinion Research Center sampled adult Americans over twenty-one years of age (N = 1325). Income was found to be highly related to the value "a comfortable life (a prosperous life)." As income increased, the value "a comfortable life (a prosperous life)" became less important.

The long-term deprivation of money may follow the hunger model just as would the short-term deprivation of money. However, the long-term effects are likely to be more pervasive than the short-term effects, and long-term deprivation is likely to affect enduring values which continue long after deprivation occurs. It is likely that the long-term deprivation of money in childhood would be related to a higher valuing of money currently.

2. Love Deprivation and the Value of Love

The hunger model would predict that deprivation of love would lead to an increase in the value of love, and that the continued receiving of love would lead to a devaluation of love. The literature is divided here between experimental social psychologists and clinicians and personality theorists.

The latter group (Fromm, 1956; Rogers, 1961; Maslow, 1954, 1962) has observed that one must have received love early in life to value it currently. They would predict a positive relationship between receiving love and the capacity to give it or to appreciate it. Experimental evidence has shown that the chronic deprivation of love early in life leads to severe intellectual, emotional, and physical damage (Boatman & Szurek, 1960; Bowlby, 1965; Goldfarb, 1961; Harlow, 1958; Harlow & Griffin, 1965; Spitz, 1946).

Bowlby (1965) in his work Child Care and the Growth of Love distinguishes between the effects of partial and complete deprivation of love:

The ill-effects of deprivation vary with its degree. Partial deprivation brings in its train anxiety, excessive need for love, powerful feelings of revenge and, arising from the last, guilt and depression. A young child, still immature in mind and body, cannot cope with all these emotions and drives. The ways in which he responds to these

disturbances of his inner life may in the end bring about nervous disorders and instability of character. Complete deprivation...has even more far-reaching effects on character development and may entirely cripple the capacity to make relationships with other people. (p. 14)

When subjects are experimentally deprived of love for short periods of time in the laboratory, they behave as though they have increased in their valuing of love (Berscheid & Walster, 1969; Dittes, 1959; Gewirtz & Baer, 1958; Walster, 1965). Both Walster (1965) and Dittes (1959) found that when subjects felt rejected or devalued as a result of the experimental manipulation, they wanted to affiliate more with others. Gewirtz and Baer (1958) demonstrated that the value of social reinforcers for children increased with deprivation. These studies represent the effects of short-term deprivation of love and show support for Homans' (1958, 1961) hypotheses.

Rokeach (1973) presents data supporting a direct relationship between values and needs, although the data are not sufficient to merit that conclusion. In a study with Berman, he investigated the relationship between need for achievement, need for power, and need for affiliation and values by administering the TAT and Rokeach's value survey to a group of college students. The TAT measures needs resulting from early social interactions (long-term).

Need for achievement was most positively correlated with the values "independent" and "intellectual," and was most negatively correlated with the values "honest" and "obedient." Values expected to be correlated with need for achievement (i.e., "a sense of accomplishment," "ambitious," and "capable") were not significantly related. Need for power was most positively correlated with "freedom" and most negatively correlated with "obedient." The value "social recognition" was not related to need for power.

Relationships between need for affiliation and Rokeach's values of love are most relevant and interesting. Need for affiliation was found to be most positively correlated with the values "true friendship" and "a world at peace." This would support a direct need-to-value relationship. However, the need for affiliation was not related to "loving" (this should have been a positively correlated relationship), or to the value "mature love" (this was actually the largest significant negative correlation with need for affiliation).

The long-term or temporary deprivation distinction is important when considering the value of love. The studies showing long-term deprivation of love are not consistent with a hunger model interpretation. The

relationships between resource income and happiness, there are also expected qualitative differences between the resources and the formation of the value of resources in relation to the hunger model.

Money, the least particularistic resource, is expected to be least related to happiness and is expected to follow the hunger model of motivation. Love, the most particularistic resource, is expected to be most related to happiness and is not expected to follow the hunger model of motivation with respect to long-term deprivation of love in childhood - where the exchange of love may be most important to the formation of enduring personality traits.

If love is the resource most related to happiness, then its exchange should be most ego involving and ego-threatening. It is likely that the deprivation of love would not only be related to a great deal of unhappiness, but also to the formation of values serving an ego-defensive function. The devaluation of love may serve to protect the individual from the anxiety associated with intimacy or the exchange of love. Since money may be less associated with happiness, the lack of it would not be likely to lead to an ego-defensive devaluation of money. Rather money and its valuation would follow the hunger model.

A distinction between needs and values is essential to this discussion. Needs refer to a lack or deficiency, while values refers to a relative preference. When the hunger model is applicable to the situation, needs and values are directly related (i.e., the greater the need, the greater the value). But values may also serve an ego-defensive function (Adorno et al., 1950; Allport, 1954; Allport & Ross, 1967; Rokeach, 1969a, 1969b), just as attitudes may serve an ego-defensive function (Katz, 1960). The devaluation of love relative to preferences for the less intimate resources may be considered ego-defensive, in that the devaluation of love may serve to avoid the anxiety associated with the exchange of intimate resources.

The increased valuing of a resource which requires little intimacy as a function of avoiding intimacy may be interpreted as a value compensation or substitution. Here again the distinction between values and needs becomes important, since that which may be needed may not be at all related to that which is valued, or vice versa. However, values and needs are often confused, used interchangeably, or are considered to be related directly to one another as in the hunger model (Homans, 1958, 1961; Maslow, 1954, 1959, 1962; Rokeach, 1973).

3. Values as Substitutes or Compensations:

The Effects of Love Poverty

Long-term love poverty may not only lead to the relative devaluing of love, but the increased valuing of the resources involving less intimacy such as information, goods, and money as well. This would imply that a maladaptive system of values may result from long-term deprivation of love. That is, a system of values may develop based on the avoidance of a needed resource (love), whereby the individual will seek resources least likely to fulfill the actual need or deficiency. The use of money or goods as substitutes or compensations for love poverty may be more common than the use of information.

The valuing of information or intellectual stimulation may be an indication of an avoidance of feelings associated with intimacy. The preference of dealing with interpersonal issues as intellectual problems, or retreat into an abstract intellectual realm, may give an individual a feeling of security, if that individual can more easily manipulate ideas than deal effectively with intimacy. However, this form of substitution may be limited to a population with the intellectual capacity or fund of knowledge to use "information" so pervasively, whereas the exchange of money and goods is not limited or restricted in such a way.

Most anyone can easily exchange money and goods. The use of money and goods as substitute resources may occur for several reasons: (1) stimulus generalization and avoidance, (2) ability to exchange and availability of resources, (3) emotional transference and risk-taking, (4) awareness of needs, and (5) learned associations.

Stimulus Generalization and Avoidance

According to Foa's (1971; Foa & Foa, 1974) proximity hypothesis, the resources closest to one another are most easily substitutable. That is, if one is denied love, then he would be most likely to seek status or services as a substitute. Money, being the furthest resource from love, would be the least acceptable substitute for love. However, if an individual, as a result of long-term love poverty, comes to defensively avoid particularistic resource exchanges, he should be most likely to seek resources involving the least amount of intimacy such as money and goods. The preference for resources should follow a stimulus generalization pattern along the particularism dimension. Therefore, the less similar a resource is to love, the greater should be its relative value.

Ability to Exchange and Availability of Resources

As already discussed, intellectual capacity or

general fund of knowledge of an individual places restrictions on the tendency to exchange information. Money and goods are more concrete resources than information and their exchange is often more easily understood. Individuals who had, as role models, persons who themselves did not adequately know how to exchange love, may not have learned how to exchange affection (Harlow, 1958). The exchange of economic resources is more easily taught and is generally integrated into the curriculum of educational institutions. The exchange of love is generally learned from one's family of origin, and there is little opportunity for learning its exchange thereafter.

Since the exchange of intimate resources may be highly ego involving, a person may be hesitant to think of himself as a learner of intimate exchange - as compared to the student of intellectual or economic resource exchange. The individual learning to cope with the economic exchanges in life may go to any of several educational institutions, whereby he would not only contribute to his learning, but would probably increase his status in the community as well. Educational degrees are considered to be signs of status and achievement.

There are few places outside of the family to learn how to exchange intimate resources. The learning that occurs

in the family may not follow rational educational goals as does the learning in formal educational institutions. The child's role in the family may be a function of the parents' needs, and this may be counter to the child's self-actualization and development. As an adult, this individual may continue to deal with others according to what was learned in the earlier relationship with his parents (Berne, 1961; Harris, 1973). Yet a person who seeks to learn to exchange intimate resources effectively through psychotherapy may be labeled by society as "sick" (Laing, 1967; Szasz, 1960).

Not only are economic resources easier to exchange, but they are generally more available to anyone - regardless of one's ability to be intimate. A person's maturity may have a greater effect on how he exchanges love than on how he exchanges money and goods. The less mature a person is, the less satisfying the exchange of love may be. A lonely person may have greater difficulty in seeking love than he would in buying an ego-gratifying material object.

Emotional Transference and Risk-Taking

Love may evoke the most emotional transference, especially since love cannot be exchanged with just anyone (Foa, 1971; Foa & Foa, 1974). The exchange of love

often involves intimacy similar to the intimacy experienced in one's family of origin. The expectations, fears, and ambivalence of childhood may be projected onto the present situation. This transference, in turn, interferes with the effective exchange of love. People may not only transfer feelings from the past to the present, but may also transfer their feelings onto other objects representing greater security or reward potential.

In psychoanalytic theory (Freud, 1963), a child may seek attachment and fusion with the loved object - primarily the mother. This attachment means security and survival. Eventually with development, the child will become more differentiated from cathected love attachments. However, if the child's interpersonal needs are overly frustrated or overly gratified to the extent that further growth is discouraged, the child - and later as an adult - will try to fuse with others, demanding total security and completeness. If attachment to others has been particularly unrewarding or discouraged, an attachment to more concrete security objects may develop. Attachments to material objects are far less demanding of the individual's maturity and they may provide a safer investment than attachments to people, as people have the power to reject or abandon.

Rejection is unlikely to occur in the exchange of money or goods. As long as one has the money, he may purchase whatever goods he desires. Money in the bank or material goods represent greater security than an investment of love when the individual has experienced repeated failures in the exchange of love.

Awareness of Needs

Few people are as aware of their love needs as they are of their economic needs. The need for love is more subtle and its awareness may even be ego-threatening. People may be more likely to admit to needing money and goods than they are to admit to needing love (Foa, 1971; Foa & Foa, 1974).

Learned Associations

The giving of gifts as an expression of love, the expression of love for children through material objects, and the use of goods as a compensation for lack of expressed love all contribute to the association of love and material objects. I am reminded here of the jingle which has currently been played as the background music of an advertisement espousing saving money for your children's futures: "Put a little love away..."

Advertising persuades us that material goods will satisfy our interpersonal insecurities. Packard's (1957)

the Hidden Persuaders gives many examples of how advertising may lead people to believe that their interpersonal needs could be eliminated by the purchase of certain products. Kassarian and Robertson's (1973) review of motivational and personality factors in consumer behavior stressed the importance of the love needs of most individuals:

In middle class America, most individuals seem to be attempting to satisfy their love or esteem needs, since their basic needs generally are satisfied. If advertising at all reflects the American need structure, this becomes evident from a casual perusal of present-day ads. (p. 115)

The actual purchase of goods may have a temporary effect of lifting one's hopes and alleviating depression. This temporary effect may reinforce the buying behavior to the extent that the individual may be tempted to buy again when he feels depressed, alone, or alienated.

4. Love Poverty in Childhood and Currently and the Values of Money and Goods

Both financial security and material goods may function as substitutes or compensations for a deficiency in love. Each may represent long-term love poverty during different periods in an individual's life. It is expected that love poverty in childhood would be related to a higher valuing of money (financial security) currently,

and that long-term love poverty currently would be related to a higher relative valuing of goods (materialism) currently.

The importance of financial security is often communicated to the child as a function of the degree of interpersonal conflict within the family unit. While love needs may be difficult to express, money needs are not. Financial need is easily measurable and presentable. Spouses may accuse each other of not being adequate wage earners, or adequate in handling money, or children may be thought of as financial burdens or liabilities. The lack of money may be used as the grounds for a disagreement while the family's actual deficiency may be the more intimate need for love. A child from the love poor family may later seek financial security, since the lack of money has been associated with interpersonal neediness and insecurity.

A person who is experiencing current love poverty may not be able to satisfy his love needs immediately, that is, if he is aware of them at all. The easiest resource to obtain is goods or material commodities. Goods don't require a relationship to be exchanged (Foa, 1971; Foa & Foa, 1974), or maturity, physical attractiveness, and intelligence - just money. The effect of purchasing a

valued material object does make the individual feel happier temporarily. This, in turn, should reinforce buying behavior when one may be unhappy due to interpersonal resource needs.

D. Maladaptive Values and the Quality of Life

Love may be our most important resource: it may be fundamental to the formation of values, which guide our choices and life styles, and it may be the resource most related to the quality of life. A long-term deficiency of love may not only significantly decrease an individual's degree of life satisfaction or general state of happiness, but may also lead to the formation of compensatory or substitute values which may perpetuate the need for love and consequently insure the individual's continued lower quality of life.

The following research was developed to assess the relationships between resources and the quality of life and to determine how the individual might develop values which keep him from obtaining the resources he needs for a higher quality of life. Fundamental to this research was the development of an objective measure of interpersonal and economic resource incomes and an objective measure of the relative value of resources.

II. HYPOTHESES

Resources and Happiness

Hypothesis 1.0: It was hypothesized that the current receiving of resources would be significantly correlated with happiness. RIS

Hypothesis 1.1: It was hypothesized that the more particularistic the resource, the higher would be the correlation between resource income and happiness. RIS

Resources and Values

Hypothesis 2.0: It was hypothesized that economic poverty in childhood would be related to a relative higher valuing of money currently. RIS
RAVIR

Hypothesis 2.1: It was hypothesized that love poverty in childhood would be related to a relative lower valuing of love currently. RIS
RAVIR

Love Poverty and Value Substitution

Hypothesis 3.0: It was hypothesized that love poverty in childhood would be related to an increased relative valuing of money currently. RIS
RAVIR

Hypothesis 3.1: It was hypothesized that current love poverty would be related to an increased relative valuing of goods currently. RIS
RAVIR

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Measuring Values - Long-term Resource Incomes and Happiness

The hypotheses of this research involve the effects of long-term social exchanges upon values and one's general state of happiness. Unfortunately, behavioral scientists have tended to avoid such issues due to the methodological problems involved in researching long-term effects. In particular, the study of values (which are predicted to result from long-term influences) has been neglected especially when compared with the study of attitudes. Rokeach (1968, 1973) argued that although values are a more basic concept than attitudes, social psychologists have been more concerned with attitudes since: (1) there were better methods for measuring attitudes, (2) there was a better consensus on the meaning of attitudes, and (3) attitudes were believed to be more amenable to experimental manipulations than were values.

We emphasized the persuasive effects of group pressure, prestige, order of communication, role playing, and forced compliance on attitudes, but we neglected the more difficult study of the more enduring effects of socialization, educational innovation, psychotherapy, and cultural change on values. (p. 158, 1968)

Rokeach claims that values deserve more study than attitudes, especially since values are the determinants of attitudes, as well as behavior; and that there are few basic values while there are a great many possible

attitudes. Studying values may be far more economical in distinguishing between groups, cultures, or persons:

It was, therefore, our hope that in shifting from a concern with attitudes to a concern with values we would be dealing with a concept that is more central, more dynamic, more economical, a concept that would invite a more enthusiastic interdisciplinary collaboration, and that would broaden the range of the social psychologists' traditional concern to include problems of education and re-education as well as problems of persuasion. (p. 159, 1968)

Shaw and Costanzo's (1971) criticism of Homans' concept of values in social exchange reflects the methodological concern with measuring values and long-term exchanges: "The varied activities involved in social relationships would be difficult to classify on a single scale of value. The assessment of an individual's past social reinforcement history is virtually impossible." (p. 81)

The first task of this research was to develop instruments to measure the relative exchange value of interpersonal resources, long-term resource incomes, and happiness. The development of these measures will be discussed in "The Development of the Research Instruments," section IV. The test of the relative exchange value of interpersonal resources, or the "REVIR" test, and the Resource Income Survey, which includes a measure of the general state of happiness, were administered to full and part-

time, day and evening, undergraduate students at Temple University during the fall semester of 1973.

Six hundred and sixty-nine (669) students were administered the REVIR IV test, and three hundred and forty-six (346) students were also administered the Resource Income Survey. Several sampling procedures and various groups were used in the development of the REVIR test. They will be detailed in section IV. Temple's day and evening classes provided a wide range of individuals from varied cultural and economic groups.

The data were collected in the classrooms with classes intact. All students were asked to cooperate, and although participation was not mandatory, very few students preferred not to participate. Students were administered the REVIR test and the Resource Income Survey as part of a values clarification workshop. They scored their own REVIR tests and were given the opportunity to relate their values to a lecture on interpersonal resource exchange and the quality of life.

It was emphasized that the students would gain a better understanding of themselves and get the most out of the workshop if they were honest in responding to the questionnaires. There was also a personal appeal that the researcher needed to rely on their honesty in order to obtain valid data necessary for his dissertation.

Students were not required to use their real names if they so desired. This additional possibility for anonymity was used to encourage the more reticent student to be more self-disclosing and honest (Kidder & Campbell, 1970).

The assistants helping to collect the data were unaware of the specific hypotheses of the research, thus helping to control for possible experimenter bias.

B. Resources and Happiness

The Resource Income Survey was administered to three hundred and forty-six students. Each resource income scale was correlated with the happiness scale. A step-wise linear regression and a 3 X 3 (love X money) ANOV statistical procedure were also utilized. Resource incomes served as the independent variables while happiness served as the dependent measure.

C. Resource Incomes in Childhood and Current Values

Three hundred and forty-six day and evening students were administered the REVIR IV test and the Resource Income Survey. An ANOV multifactorial design was used to assess possible interactions or non-linear effects. A 2 X 4 (love X money) ANOV was performed on the dependent measures in assessing the effects of past

resource incomes. Family yearly money income during childhood (item 9) and childhood love income (item 1), as measured by the Resource Income Survey, served as the independent variables. Values, as measured by the REVIR test, served as the dependent measures. The sample was divided into high and low love income families (via median split), and into low, low-middle, high-middle, and high financial income families (via ranking and equal sub-division into four groups).

Two levels of childhood love income were thought to be sufficient. It was feared that greater sub-division would only increase the probability of erroneous findings. However, extreme groups of money income were needed with this predominantly middle class student sample. It was assumed that there would be less of an error involved in scaling financial income than in scaling love income.

D. Resource Incomes Currently and Values

A 3 X 3 (love X money) ANOV design was used to assess the effects of current resource incomes upon values. Since money income was not expected to be significantly related to current values, a division involving more than three levels was not necessary. Three levels of both factors would allow for the assessment of possible curvilinear relationships. Current

yearly money income (item 10) and current love income (item 2) served as the independent variables. The sample was ranked by love and money incomes and then divided into high, medium, and low income groups.

Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics of the sample. The sample includes a wide range of individuals, from those with poverty backgrounds to those who came from affluent families. Although this research was restricted to a college sample, it includes a wide enough range of individuals with various economic backgrounds to be sufficient to deal with the research hypotheses. (Reference to the values of the sample as shown in table 1 is premature here, since the REVIR test is first introduced in the following section. However, the values of this sample are included so that they may be compared with normative sample values. N = 669)

TABLE 1

SUBJECT
POPULATION CHARACTERISTICS
(N=346, f=166, m=180)

<u>AGE</u>	$\bar{X} = 23.0$	s.d. = 7.5	range = 16-61						
<u>INCOME IN CHILDHOOD</u>	$\bar{X} = 5.0$	s.d. = 2.4							
scale number	<u>1</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>3</u>	<u>4</u>	<u>5</u>	<u>6</u>	<u>7</u>	<u>8</u>	<u>9</u>
<u>\$1000 per year</u>	<1	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	16+
<u>number of S's</u>	5	10	25	63	65	51	50	28	49
ANOV factors	/...../...../.....		LO	LO-MID			HI-MID	HI	
<u>INCOME CURRENTLY</u>	$\bar{X} = 5.7$	s.d. = 2.1							
scale number	<u>1</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>3</u>	<u>4</u>	<u>5</u>	<u>6</u>	<u>7</u>	<u>8</u>	<u>9</u>
<u>\$1000 per year</u>	<1	1-3	3-6	6-9	9-12	12-15	15-18	18-21	21+
<u>number of S's</u>	21	49	36	38	59	43	37	24	39
ANOV factors	/...../.....		LO	MID			HI		
<u>VALUES</u>	MN	GD	SR	SX	LV	ST	IN		
$\bar{X} =$	9.7	6.2	8.3	9.2	10.4	8.4	10.8		
s.d. =	3.7	4.9	3.5	3.3	3.8	3.2	4.1		

IV. THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE RESEARCH INSTRUMENTS

In order to research the various hypotheses, several measures had to be developed (i.e., a test for measuring the relative exchange value of interpersonal resources, a survey measuring both economic and non-economic resources incomes, and a measure of happiness). All of the instruments developed for this research were theoretically based on Foa's (1971; Foa & Foa, 1974) resource exchange theory.

A. The REVIR Test: A Test of the Relative Exchange Value of Interpersonal Resources

A test was developed to measure a person's or a groups's relative exchange value of interpersonal resources (REVIR). The test was designed so that it would indicate a value system representing the basic interpersonal orientation or life style of the individual. The test includes all the main resources specified in Foa's resource model (i.e., money, goods, services, love, status, and information). An additional resource "sex" was included in the REVIR test as well as the surveys. Sex would be an intermediate resource between love and services in Foa's structural model (see fig. 1). Sex was included as a resource since it is an important variable in people's life styles and interpersonal orientations.

1. Structure

Our real life choices and commitments define our

values. The REVIR test was constructed to reflect value choices that could occur in fantasy or in actual vocational and marital choices. The choices within the fantasy or "wish" dimension may reflect what we would like without the constraints of social institutions, conformity, or norms. Actual choices within work or family institutions are somewhat more restricted. Particular institutions are characterized by the resources which are typically exchanged there.

Foa and Donnenwerth (1971) consider this institutional resource differentiation.

Cultural norms are quite specific with regard to the resources which can be used in a given institution...Moreover, it seems that in each institution certain means of exchange are more typical and significant, although other means may appear as well in interactions within the institution. The exchange of money-services appears to be typical of the work situation; the exchange of money-information of the school institution (if private) or status-information (if public); money-goods exchange is typical of the trade institution. In the family, love and status appear to be crucial resources. (p. 151)

There is a good deal of interrelationships between institutions as well, or what Rapoport and Rapoport (1971) called: "...a general tendency toward isomorphism, or similarity of behavior patterning, exists between the major life spheres." (p. 279)

Oeser and Hammond (1954) argued that an individual's interpersonal behavior in both the work and family situations

will be similar due to the individual's beliefs and expectations about himself and others. Therefore, a person who values love should value it in both the work and family situations. The exchange of love and status is extremely important in the work situation. Even purely task oriented groups' productivity is affected by the groups' social emotional climate (Argyris, 1962; Bennis, 1966). The task of the groups will suffer as the interpersonal relationships suffer. Issues of power, status, allegiance, and friendship are often ignored or discounted in spite of their importance to the achievement of task oriented goals.

Just as the work situation is also dependent on the exchange of particularistic resources (i.e., love and status), the family is dependent upon the exchange of the economic resources in addition to the particularistic ones. The lack of financial security within a family will produce frustration and anxiety which may then interfere with the exchange of particularistic resources (Bronfenbrenner, 1958; Hess & Shipman, 1967; McKinley, 1964; Lewis, 1966). The culture of poverty (Harrington, 1962) involves the deprivation of interpersonal particularistic resources as well as universal economic resources, which may result in a value system which perpetuates the culture of poverty (Moynihan, 1966, 1967).

Rapoport and Rapoport (1971) argue that a person

can choose and structure both work and family situations according to his own personality needs and his relations with others.

Family and work are no longer subject to a single over-arching set of role prescriptions in an integrated cultural whole, nor are family functions as residual as they are when work is either over-valued or alienative, as it was in the era following the industrial revolution. Individuals now have a wider range of possibilities to consider in choosing both work and spouse, and greater freedom in organizing family life in relation to job requirements. (p. 245)

The type of person we would prefer to marry or the type of work we would prefer to do reflects our values. They are two of the three areas on the REVIR test. Each of the three areas are presented with choices between the seven resources. For example, a choice between the resources money and information for the "wish" area would be as follows:

If I had my choice between two wishes, I would wish for...

- (a) financial security
- (b) great knowledge and wisdom

For the "work" area a choice between money and information would be:

If I had my choice between two otherwise similar jobs, I would prefer...

- (a) to work where I could earn an excellent income
- (b) to work at a job which is intellectually stimulating

For the "spouse" area a choice between money and information would be:

If I had my choice between two otherwise similar people, I would prefer to marry...

(a) someone who could contribute to the financial security of the family

(b) someone very intelligent

If a resource is chosen every time, that resource will have a value of "6" for that area. If the resource is chosen every time in all three areas, it will have a value of "18."

When an overall total score from each resource is tallied, they are listed in order from the most chosen to the least chosen resource. This represents the individual's value system or the relative exchange value of interpersonal resources.

Self-scoring answer and scoring sheets were developed so that an item is scored as the individual takes the test. This provides an individual with immediate feedback upon completion of the test, and acts as a check that no items are missed and that in no case two items are chosen instead of the required one. The totals of each area should equal "21" and the overall total should equal "63." (See copies of the REVIR answer and scoring sheets in the Appendix.)

The items were worded so that the overall total means

for each resource would fall midscale - around "9" in a possible range of zero to eighteen. This involved constant revision of the REVIR test. The revisions of the money items involved increasing their desirability; for example, rewording marrying "someone who provided financial security" to marrying "someone who could help contribute to the financial security of the family." (Even this subtle rewording was significant. The latter form included the feeling of volition as opposed to that of obligation.) The love items were reworded to decrease their desirability as with changing marrying "someone very affectionate" to marrying "someone extremely affectionate." ("Extremely" is more difficult to define, but may be more ego-threatening to someone who is defensive about intimacy.)

A sample of day and evening students at Temple University (N = 669) were administered the REVIR IV test. The results show that all the means were mid-range with the highest value being information ($\bar{X} = 10.9$) and the lowest value being goods ($\bar{X} = 7.2$). These means would be expected from a college sample (see table 2).

2. Paired Comparison Scaling

Paired comparison scaling was used for the REVIR test. Likert scaling poorly discriminated between the values since the resources, by definition, are all valuable. Also, it would

TABLE 2

REVIR ~~IV~~-MEAN SCORES FOR COLLEGE STUDENTS

(N=669, f=307, m=362) TOTAL RANGE=0-18

<u>AREA</u>	<u>MN</u>	<u>GD</u>	<u>SR</u>	<u>SX</u>	<u>LV</u>	<u>ST</u>	<u>IN</u>
WISH	3.0	2.1	2.8	3.5	3.4	2.7	3.6
WORK	4.1	2.8	2.6	1.7	2.8	2.5	4.6
SPOUSE	3.2	2.2	2.9	3.7	3.2	2.9	2.8
OVER- ALL TOTAL	10.2	7.2	8.2	8.9	9.4	8.1	10.9
(s.d.)	3.7	4.9	3.4	3.3	3.9	3.3	4.0

not reflect a value system in that it would not indicate how the values are interrelated in terms of preference. The rank order method does show relative preferences and does indicate a value system. Ranking is quick and there is no complex scoring involved, but there are several problems with ranking. Ranking produces the most ipsative data - choosing one item limits the number of choices for each thereafter. Ranking does not allow for ties, and in reality, equal preferences are common. Rankings may produce a "U" shaped relationship between order of presentation and reliability.

Rokeach's (1973) value survey, based on rank ordering of two lists with eighteen values on each, indicates both high test - retest stability for the first and the last few values, and low test - retest stability for the middle values. There was a significant correlation of .43 between the order in which the values were presented and the median value rankings of the instrumental values. Ranking becomes a difficult task when the number of items to be ranked is large. Rokeach's value survey of eighteen terminal values and eighteen instrumental values makes the ranking process difficult, and lowers the validity and the reliability of the test. The optimum bits of information that an individual can keep in his immediate attention span is about seven plus

or minus two (Miller, 1956). After ranking a list of eighteen terminal values, when the respondent may be fatigued, he is then required to rank another eighteen instrumental values. Of the thirteen test - retest studies presented by Rokeach (1973) of the ranked terminal and instrumental values, twelve showed higher correlations for the terminal values than for the instrumental values. In the remaining study, they were equal. In all of the studies the terminal values were presented first. This indicates that the respondents tended to be fatigued by the time they were working on the second ranking task.

Rokeach's values are not theoretically based, and perhaps this lack of a theoretical base allowed for the high number of values (36). The Allport, Vernon and Lindzey (1960) study of values was based on Spranger's personality theory - allowing for just six values. The REVIR test allows for seven values, which are founded in Foa's theory of interpersonal resource exchange.

Only the REVIR test uses the paired comparisons method. An individual has only to decide between two value choices at one time, and at the end the total number of times that value was chosen against the other values represents the weight of that value. Ties are possible. The individual can get a total concept of his

value system in its entirety by simply viewing the relative values of the seven scores. The REVIR test can be taken and self-scored in about twenty minutes. Its reading level allows for a wide range of persons - from junior high school age to college students. The Allport, Vernon and Lindzey (1960) study of values was designed for use with college students and the items often reflect academic interests. The REVIR test permits a wide range of individuals to readily score and easily understand their value systems as they relate to a theory of interpersonal resource exchange.

3. Items

As previously mentioned, each item was worded so that it would have a particular average weight. The items were worded so that the total overall mean scores would be about mid-scale. With an overall total possible range of zero to eighteen (0-18), the average score should be about "9" (plus or minus 2). On the REVIR IV this weighting was accomplished. The items on the REVIR IV and V are all presented here so that comparisons between the forms could be made, as well as to facilitate understanding of the scales. (The REVIR V is presented in this section only. The REVIR V involved some rewording of the "sex" and "status" scales to improve internal consistency. Although the REVIR V was not used in this research,

it is included here for reference in future research.)

a. Area Questions

Wish - If I had my choice between two wishes, I would prefer...

Work - If I had my choice between two otherwise similar jobs, I would prefer...

Spouse - If I had my choice between two otherwise similar people, I would prefer to marry...

b. Items of the REVIR Forms IV and V

MONEY Wish - to have financial security.

Work - to work where I would earn an excellent income.

Spouse - someone who could contribute to the financial security of the family.

GOODS Wish - to have a life of wealth and luxury.

Work - to have a position where I could enjoy luxuries and material wealth.

Spouse - someone with whom I could share a life of wealth and luxury.

SERVICES Wish - to always have the availability of helpful people.

Work - to have a position where I would have skillful people to help me with my work.

Spouse - someone helpful to have around.

- SEX Wish - to have a fulfilling sex life.
Work - to have a position where I could associate with many attractive people. (IV)
to work where I would have the opportunity to meet sexually attractive people. (V)
Spouse - someone for whom I would feel sexual attraction.
- LOVE Wish - to always have a great many close friends.
Work - to work where everyone would express a lot of affection for each other.
Spouse - someone extremely affectionate.
- STATUS Wish - to be held in very high esteem by people I admire. (IV)
to be respected by people I admire. (V)
Work - to work where I would have a position of high status. (IV)
to work where I would have a position of high respect. (V)
Spouse - someone who would make me feel important.
- INFORMATION Wish - to have great knowledge and wisdom.
Work - to work at a job which is intellectually stimulating.
Spouse - someone very intelligent.

c. Item Analysis

The REVIR test involves making value choices within three independent areas (wish, work, and spouse). The value of a resource is not only a function of the number of times it was chosen within an area but also how often it was chosen across areas. A person who values love a great deal in the spouse area may not necessarily value love much in the other two areas. This specificity affects the relative value of love. A person who values love a good deal in all three areas is considered to place a higher value on love than the individual whose valuing of love is restricted to one specific area. Our cultural expectations usually differentiate among areas or institutions in the exchange of different resources. Money can be exchanged most anywhere whereas sex cannot. There are strong legal and social sanctions against it. A normal individual is expected to make some differentiation among the areas.

The REVIR test is structured so that a certain amount of differentiation is expected among the areas. Each value scale is really a combination of three distinct value choice areas. This structure makes most measures of internal consistency inappropriate. Yet overlap is expected (see "1. structure"). In order to justify using total overall scores, the overlap should be significant. A presentation

of correlations of each area with the overall total for each resource would provide the most descriptive information of internal consistency for each value scale. (The term "correlation" used throughout this research refers to the standard product-moment correlation with a base of zero.) The item analysis shows that each area is highly correlated with the overall total score of each value scale. All the correlations were well beyond the .001 level of significance (see table 3).

The internal consistency was generally improved with the REVIR V, particularly for the "status" scale (see table 4). The lowest correlation was for sex in the work area ($r = .53$). This item remained low in spite of the more specific rewording (see the preceding section "b. items of the REVIR forms IV and V"). This seems to suggest that people are particularly careful in differentiating where to exchange sex and the work area is clearly differentiated from the other areas. As one student expressed after noting that she had scored very high in the wish and spouse areas for sex but low in the work area, "When I work I work, when I play I play."

4. Norms

The REVIR IV test was administered to six hundred and sixty-nine day and evening students from Temple University (307 females & 362 males). The overall total means for each

TABLE 3

CORRELATIONS OF EACH AREA WITH THE OVER-ALL
TOTAL SCORE FOR EACH SCALE FOR
THE REVIR IV TEST (N=669)

<u>AREA</u>	<u>MN</u>	<u>GD</u>	<u>SR</u>	<u>SX</u>	<u>LV</u>	<u>ST</u>	<u>IN</u>
WISH	.76	.87	.72	.73	.69	.64	.77
WORKER	.73	.87	.70	.57	.73	.54	.72
SPOUSE	.70	.82	.67	.69	.65	.66	.73

TABLE 4

CORRELATIONS OF EACH AREA WITH THE OVER-ALL
TOTAL SCORE FOR EACH SCALE FOR
THE REVIR V TEST (N=65)

<u>AREA</u>	<u>MN</u>	<u>GD</u>	<u>SR</u>	<u>SX</u>	<u>LV</u>	<u>ST</u>	<u>IN</u>
WISH	.90	.89	.84	.84	.72	.81	.83
WORKER	.70	.90	.81	.53	.79	.71	.70
SPOUSE	.83	.84	.78	.87	.77	.75	.87

scale fall mid-scale - about "9" plus or minus two (see table 2).

5. Intercorrelations Between the Scales

The REVIR test is composed of seven scales indicating various interpersonal resources. The resources would be expected to be intercorrelated since they are theoretically based on Foa's (1971) structural model. However, the resources should be independent enough of each other to warrant separate scaling. The intercorrelations are presented in table 5. The largest positive correlation between any two scales was only .22 - between money and goods. The largest correlations were negative: -.44 between love and goods and -.43 between love and money. These correlations do not justify reducing the seven scales to a smaller number.

6. Stability Over Time

Values are relatively enduring over time, even more so than attitudes since values are more basic than attitudes and should therefore be more resistant to change. Allport (1937) suggested that values can become "functionally autonomous" continuing to exist long after the need or reinforcement has ended. Any test of values should reflect this characteristic stability. Allport, Vernon and Lindzey (1960) report a mean repeat reliability coefficient of .89 for a one month test - retest

TABLE 5

INTERCORRELATIONS OF THE REVIR IV SCALES (N=669)

	MN	GD	SR	SX	LV	ST	IN
MN	--	.22	-.14	-.29	-.43	-.18	-.21
GD	.22	--	-.41	-.19	-.44	-.11	-.37
SR	-.14	-.41	--	-.22	.04	-.08	-.04
SX	-.29	-.19	-.22	--	.17	-.15	-.09
LV	-.43	-.44	.04	.17	--	-.09	-.07
ST	-.18	-.11	-.08	-.15	-.09	--	-.11
IN	-.21	-.37	-.04	-.09	-.07	-.11	--

study, and .88 for a two month test - retest study. Rokeach's (1973) value survey averages a test - retest product moment reliability of .65 for the terminal values and .60 for the instrumental values. Sixty-three students were administered the REVIR IV test twice with a two week interval between testings. The lowest correlation was .70 for services and the highest correlation was .86 for goods. The mean test - retest correlation for the seven scales was .79 (see table 6). All of the REVIR test scales appear to be highly reliable over time.

7. Social Approval

The need for social approval can affect the validity of a test such as the REVIR test. An individual who is confronted with a "psychological test" is often concerned with how to present himself. A person with a high need for social approval might be more likely to try to present himself on a test or survey in a manner that would place him in the best possible light. His main concern would be to look good and not necessarily to be honest. Crowne and Marlowe (1964) developed a scale to measure the need for social approval or "social desirability." The social desirability (S-D) scale is significantly correlated with the correction factor (K), lie (L), and fake (F) scales on the MMPI (.40 for K, .54 for L, and -.36

TABLE 6

REVIR IV TEST-RETEST (2 WEEKS) CORRELATIONS (N=63)

MN	.82
GD	.86
SR	.70
SX	.73
LV	.82
ST	.75
IN	.84

for F). For example, people who score high on the S-D scale would tend to agree with the following items:

"I have never intensely disliked anyone."

"I am always courteous, even to people who are disagreeable."

The scale measures the need for social approval by assuming that people with a high need for social approval will seek social approval by presenting themselves in an unrealistic overly conscientious way, while distorting or denying unpleasant and unacceptable aspects of themselves.

The REVIR test controls for this need to look good in several ways: (1) All of the resources are desirable and valuable. Unlike tests which measure psychopathology or intelligence, no one can do poorly in a test of personal values. The respondents are reminded of this as a part of the instructions for taking the REVIR test. (2) The resources are counterbalanced by the three areas. For example, it may not be socially acceptable to choose a job for its potential sexual rewards, but it may be acceptable to consider the potential sexual rewards of a spouse. (3) Each item is worded to avoid any socially undesirable connotations. Items are worded to be equally socially desirable. For example, marrying for money

would go against the cultural notion of marriage as the culmination of romantic love, but most people would not mind marrying someone rich if wealth were combined with other valuable resources in that potential spouse. On the REVIR test, a choice between marrying for love or marrying for money might be expected to be motivated in part by the need for social approval. However, on the REVIR test this comparison has been worded as marrying "someone who could contribute to the financial security of the family" or marrying "someone extremely affectionate." These two statements represent equal social desirability. The means for love and money in the spouse area are equal (3.2; see table 2).

It was hypothesized that if the REVIR test controlled for the effects of social desirability, there would be no significant relationships between the REVIR scales and the S-D scale. The REVIR IV and the Marlowe-Crowne S-D scale were administered to ninety-four students (44 females, 50 males). The results support the hypothesis.

There were no significant relationships between the S-D scale and the REVIR IV test (see table 7). An individual's scores on the REVIR test will not be significantly influenced by the need to present himself in a socially desirable way.

TABLE 7

CORRELATIONS BETWEEN THE REVIR IV
AND THE MARLOWE-CROWNE (S-D) SCALE

(N = 94, f=44, m=50)

MN	.18 n.s.
GD	.15 n.s.
SR	-.06 n.s.
SX	-.10 n.s.
LV	-.11 n.s.
ST	-.10 n.s.
IN	.07 n.s.

8. Validity

Several studies supporting the validity of the REVIR test are presented. They include studies of concurrent validity with other tests, a study indicating the REVIR test's ability to differentiate between groups, and a study indicating the test's ability to predict behavior.

a. Concurrent Validity with Rokeach's Value Survey

A sample of college students (N =47) were administered Rokeach's (1973) value survey and the REVIR IV test. Only the significant correlations are presented here. A priori hypotheses are presented along with each value. Besides the a priori hypotheses, general information was sought to gain a better understanding of the REVIR scales.

The summary conclusions based on these post hoc observations are only tentative hypotheses themselves. (Rokeach uses a ranking system so that the lower the number assigned to the value the more valuable it is. The opposite is true for the REVIR test - the higher the number assigned a value the more valuable it is. The signs for the correlations were reversed so that they would be easier to understand. Therefore, a negative sign indicates a negative relationship. To facilitate reading, the correlations are presented in quasi-tables along with the text.)

<u>REVIR Scale</u>	<u>Rokeach's Values</u>	
Money	a comfortable life	.43
	family security	.45
	pleasure	.31
	ambitious	.38
	self-controlled	.41
	a world at peace	-.36
	a world of beauty	-.30
	freedom	-.37
	true friendship	-.43
	honest	-.29
loving	-.32	

Rokeach does not have a value of money per se. It was expected, however, that the Rokeach value "a comfortable life (a prosperous life)" would be significantly positively related to the value of money on the REVIR test. The results support this hypothesis. It was further hypothesized that the value of money on the REVIR test would be negatively related to the values "true friendship (close companionship)" and "loving (affectionate, tender)" on Rokeach's value survey. This hypothesis was also supported (thereby showing support for Hypothesis 3.0 in section II).

There were no a priori hypotheses concerning Rokeach's value "mature love (sexual and spiritual

intimacy)." Erotic and agapian love are two very different things. Several personality theorists and researchers have noted this difference (Fromm, 1956; May, 1969; Reik, 1949; Rubin, 1973). By combining sexual and spiritual intimacy, the connotation "mature love" becomes confounded. Rokeach has never shown validity for this value. "Mature love" did not significantly correlate with any of the REVIR scales ($-.10$ for love and $-.14$ for sex), and it is not even significantly correlated with Rokeach's value "loving" ($-.01$).

It was also predicted that the value of money on the REVIR would be positively related to "family security" as would be suggested by Hypothesis 3.0 in section II. Overall, the value of money seems to represent a lower order concern for security and material comforts. The value of money is negatively related to values such as concern for truth, beauty, freedom, peace, love and friendship. A high value of money represents a kind of antisocial materialism.

Goods	pleasure	.58
	a comfortable life	.41
	an exciting life	.57
	a world at peace	-.42
	equality	-.45
	freedom	-.41
	salvation	-.32

Goods	forgiving	-.47
	honest	-.43
	obedient	-.30

It was hypothesized that the value of goods on the REVIR test would be significantly related to the value "a comfortable life (a prosperous life)" on Rokeach's value survey. The results indicate that the value of goods was related to "a comfortable life" as predicted. Overall, the value of goods seems to represent a selfish materialistic approach to life - a kind of egocentric hedonism.

Services	equality	.54
	freedom	.42
	salvation	.41
	courageous	.36
	honest	.32
	a world at peace	.34
	an exciting life	-.60
	a comfortable life	-.36
	a sense of accomplishment	-.31
	pleasure	-.42
	cheerful	-.42

There were no specific a priori hypotheses concerning the value of services on the REVIR test. None of

Rokeach's values were close to the value of services in concept. The Rokeach values that significantly correlated with the value of services seem to be intuitively related. A person who values services from others would seem to be principled and socially concerned - with a serious socialistic approach to life.

Sex	broadminded	.29
	obedient	-.30
	polite	-.32

The only Rokeach value which might seem to relate to the REVIR value of sex would be "mature love (sexual and spiritual intimacy)." However, as previously mentioned, the value "mature love" is confounded, and it is uncertain what this value is actually measuring. It was hypothesized that the value of sex would be related to "an exciting life (a stimulating, active life)" and "pleasure (an enjoyable, leisurely life)," in addition to "broadminded (open-minded)." The results do not indicate a significant relationship between the value of sex and "an exciting life" (.23) or "pleasure" (.15). The value of sex on the REVIR is significantly related to the value "broadminded" as predicted. Sex does not seem to reflect a hedonistic orientation, but rather an open-minded non-authoritarian orientation. This finding is consistent with the dynamics of the authoritarian personality (Adorno et al., 1950).

Love	a world at peace	.33
	freedom	.35
	true friendship	.41
	forgiving	.39
	honest	.32
	pleasure	-.36
	ambitious	-.35
	capable	-.35
	clean	-.29

It was expected that the value of love on the REVIR test would be related positively to "true friendship" and "loving." The correlation between love and "true friendship" was the highest significant relationship, while "loving" was only marginally significantly related ($.27, p < .10$; r must be at least $.288$ for $df = 45, p < .05$).

It is interesting to note which of Rokeach's values were significantly related to both love and money on the REVIR test. As would be expected, if a Rokeach value was negatively related to money, it would be positively related to love and vice versa. The Rokeach values "a world at peace," "freedom," "true friendship," and "honest" were negatively related to money and are positively related to love. "Pleasure," "ambitious," and "self-controlled" were positively related to money and are negatively related to love.

The value of love seems to reflect an orientation which views people not as a means to an end, but as an end in themselves.

Status	social recognition	.32
	broadminded	-.30

The value of status was predicted to be positively related to Rokeach's value of "social recognition (respect, admiration)." The results support this prediction. In fact, status was related to nothing else except "broadminded." The negative relationship between status and "broadminded" is consistent with the concept of the authoritarian personality (Adorno et al., 1950).

Information	a world at peace	.29
	a world of beauty	.32
	equality	.29
	wisdom	.41
	intellectual	.38
	a comfortable life	-.30
	an exciting life	-.39
	pleasure	-.33
	courageous	-.31

It was hypothesized that the value of information would be positively related to Rokeach's values "wisdom (a mature understanding of life)" and "intellectual (intelligent, reflective)." The results support this hypothesis.

The value of information reflects an orientation towards more symbolic ideals such as wisdom, beauty, peace and equality. Overall, the REVIR test's scales show excellent concurrent validity with Rokeach's value survey.

b. Concurrent Validity with Schutz's FIRO-B

The "FIRO-B" stands for "fundamental interpersonal relations orientation-behavior." That is, it measures how people tend to behaviorally relate to others. The FIRO-B was developed by Schutz (1966) based on his three dimensional theory of interpersonal behavior. The basic idea behind the theory is that people orient themselves towards others according to these three dimensions of interpersonal behavior or needs: inclusion (I), control (C), and affection (A). These dimensions are a function of the individual's early family interactions. The need for inclusion is a function of the extent to which the child was included or integrated as a family member. Control is a function of the extent to which the child's parents used control over the child. Affection is a function of the degree to which the child was given approval or rejected in the family.

The FIRO-B measures the current behaviors the individual expresses towards others (e) and the behaviors he

wants others to express towards him (w). If the values of love and money on the REVIR test are a function of love poverty in childhood as predicted, then the value of love should be positively related to wanting and expressing inclusion (Iw and Ie), and wanting and expressing affection (Aw and Ae). The value of money should show the opposite relationship, since it is predicted that a child who was accepted in his family of origin will have a higher relative value of love and a lower relative value of money.

The REVIR IV test and the FIRO-B were administered to ninety-seven students. The results support the predictions (see table 8). All the significant relationships are presented here. It is interesting to note that the value of goods on the REVIR test was not significantly correlated with any of the scales on the FIRO-B. This shows support for Hypothesis 3.1, since the value of goods was predicted to be a function of current love poverty and not love poverty originating in childhood.

The values of love and money, which were predicted to be a function of childhood love poverty, do relate to the inclusion and affection scales as hypothesized. People who place a high value on money may tend to express little desire for inclusion, little control over others, and little desire for affection. People who place a high value on love tend to have the opposite orientation. Overall,

TABLE 8

SIGNIFICANT CORRELATIONS BETWEEN THE REVIR IV AND
THE FIRO-B (N=97, f=65, m=32)

<u>MN</u>	Ie -.18	<u>LV</u>	Ie .28
	Iw -.18		Iw .36
	Ce -.20		Cw .24
	Ae -.24		Ae .34
	Aw -.25		Aw .31
<u>GD</u>	all n.s.	<u>ST</u>	Ie .23
<u>SR</u>	all n.s.		Aw .27
<u>SX</u>	Ce .31	<u>IN</u>	Ie -.25
			Iw -.17

p < .05 = .17

p < .01 = .24

p < .0005 = .33

the FIRO-B scales show excellent concurrent validity with the REVIR.

c. Values and Vocational Choices

An assumption of the REVIR test is that people will choose intimate others and work situations as a function of their personal values. In order to test this assumption, the REVIR IV was administered to various groups of individuals of different college majors at Temple University, and to a group of police from John Jay College of Criminal Justice. Social welfare majors (day students) were thought to be characterized by their pro-social (socialistic) orientation - or in terms of values, high in love and services and low in money and goods. Psychology majors, although oriented towards both social and intellectual values, were not expected to be as high in the value of services as the social welfare majors. Since they are more scientifically oriented, psychology majors were expected to be high in information. Business majors and accounting students, unlike the social welfare and psychology students, were thought to be more interested in money and goods and less interested in love and services. Management majors were expected to be similar to business students except for a higher valuing of status - since they would prefer to relate to people in terms of power and authority. The police were thought to value status a great deal and be least interested in love and service - being more

concerned with money and goods (an antisocial orientation represented in an ego-defensive materialistic value system).

It was expected that these groups would represent such differing value systems that all the scales of the REVIR would be significantly differentiated. The results shown in table 9 do support that hypothesis. All results are in the predicted directions. The range of scale scores are indicative of the test's sensitivity to value differences between groups. Social welfare majors valued love and services the most and money and goods the least. Psychology majors valued information and love the most and money and goods the least. Business and accounting majors valued money and information the most and goods and sex the least. Management majors valued money and status the most and sex and services the least. The police valued status and goods the most and love and services the least. Whereas the police had a score of 11.8 for goods, the social welfare majors had a goods score of only 3.4. The social welfare students had a love score of 13.5 as compared to the police love score of only 3.9 (this is based on an eighteen point scale). These extreme value differences between social welfare students and the police indicates the power of the REVIR test to distinguish among groups, as well as supporting the predictive validity of the REVIR.

TABLE 9

VALUES AND VOCATIONAL CHOICE

GROUP	<u>N</u>	<u>MN</u>	<u>GD</u>	<u>SR</u>	<u>SX</u>	<u>LV</u>	<u>ST</u>	<u>IN</u>
Social Welfare	f=25 m=4 29	6.8	3.4	11.6	10.5	13.5	7.6	9.7
Psychology	f=58 m=46 104	8.5	5.8	7.6	9.4	11.7	7.9	12.1
Business & Accounting	f=8 m=27 35	10.4	7.4	8.7	6.9	8.4	7.9	10.2
Management	f=4 m=19 23	12.5	9.8	7.7	7.4	9.7	11.7	9.1
Police	f=2 m=38 40	10.6	11.8	5.0	9.9	3.9	13.6*	6.9

GROUP MAIN EFFECTS
df = 4/221

F =	6.23	9.68	6.95	3.43	9.49	9.74	6.59
p <	.0003	.00001	.0002	.01	.00001	.00001	.0002
SEX MAIN EFFECTS	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
SEX X GROUP INTERACTION	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	.04*	n.s.

*based on only two females

d. Values and Volunteering for Encounter Workshops

Sensitivity training groups and encounter groups provide an opportunity to exchange affection and esteem (Foa & Donnenwerth, 1971), and provide an experience that could change one's values. In their extensive research on the effects of various forms of encounter groups or group therapies, Lieberman, Yalom and Miles (1973) found:

Consistently, the encounter groups were found to have maximum effect on values of the participants, whether participants were compared with controls or differences among the seventeen groups were assessed. The special sensitivity of values is further emphasized in the finding that the values with which participants entered the encounter groups were one of the two strongest predictors of overall outcome status. Although these value shifts were often unique to the individual, the most characteristic among the participants was an increased valuation of personal growth and change. (pp. 446-447)

People who defensively devalue love may be more likely to avoid intimate situations such as encounter groups, so that they may avoid the exchange of love that occurs and the frightening possibility of personal growth and change. Intimacy and change are threats to a value system which has been designed to avoid anxiety and to preserve cognitive consistency.

Students from a social psychology course at Temple University were offered a chance to participate in two

extra-curricular "Esalen-type" workshops, i.e., an encounter group and a massage workshop. These workshops involved a good deal of intimacy within a short period of time, and with individuals who were not well known to each other. Normally, this situation would be associated with a great deal of anxiety, but for the individual with a value system based on the avoidance of intimacy, these workshops would evoke an enormous amount of anxiety.

Two volunteer sign-up sheets, one for each workshop, were circulated among the students in class. Then the students were administered the REVIR test as a separate classroom exercise. Approximately one-half of the class volunteered for either the micro-lab encounter group or the massage workshop, or both. If a student signed both sheets indicating he wished to attend both workshops, he was assigned a "2." If the student signed up for only one workshop, he was assigned a "1." If he did not sign up for either workshop (a name appearing on the REVIR test but not on either sign-up sheet), the student was assigned a "0." These volunteer scores were then correlated with the REVIR test value scores.

It was predicted that the greater relative devaluing of love and valuing of money on the REVIR test, the less likely the student would be to have volunteered for the workshops. The results supported this hypothesis (see table 10). The more one values love, the more likely he

TABLE 10

THE CORRELATIONS BETWEEN VOLUNTEERING
FOR ENCOUNTER WORKSHOPS AND VALUES
(N=110)

<u>VALUE</u>	<u>r</u>	<u>p <</u>
MN	-.37	.001
GD	-.36	.001
SR	.06	n.s.
SX	.11	n.s.
LV	.58	.001
ST	-.14	n.s.
IN	.12	n.s.

The correlation between the Marlowe-Crowne scale and volunteering was not at all significant ($r = .00$). These results not only support the hypothesis that values predict resource seeking behavior better than a measure of needs, but also support the predictive validity of the REVIR test.

9. Uses

The REVIR test can be used as a research instrument for measuring values - as a classroom demonstration on values and interpersonal exchange, based on Foa's theory, or as a personal values clarification instrument. It can be used in vocational guidance by helping individuals to clarify their values and life goals. Since the REVIR test provides immediate feedback and can be easily interpreted, it may be used in a variety of settings and by many people.

B. A Survey of Long-term Resource Incomes in Childhood, Currently, and One's General State of Happiness

An instrument was developed to measure individual resource income, based on Foa's resource exchange theory, and one's general state of happiness. In order to test the hypotheses, it was necessary to scale non-economic resources as well as economic resources - as they were received in childhood and currently. The resources of love, status, information, money, goods, services, and sex were assessed on a nine-point bi-polar scale (with "1" as "lowest, not at all, never" and "9" as "highest, always, completely").

Wilson (1967) had argued for the use of bi-polar nine-point scales and a theoretical orientation for studying the avowed correlates of happiness.

...The designations "very happy," "pretty happy," and "not too happy"... seem as good as any... seemingly little would be lost and much gained if the above designations were used to define a nine-point, rather than a three-point scale, and if correlations, rather than tables of percentages, were reported. Correlations seem to require less space for summarization, provide a better indication of degree of relationship, and allow for a quick and easy test of significance... Further studies merely correlating happiness with numerous other variables are not recommended... studies are recommended that test theoretical expectations about the likely relationship between happiness and other specific variables... (pp. 304-305)

Scales measuring happiness have been found to be reliable and valid. Wessman and Ricks (1966) reported that happiness related measures taken two years apart correlated .67. They also found little relationship between happiness ratings and social desirability and other measures of bias.

Wilson's suggestions were incorporated in the development of both the long-term and recent exchange surveys, as well as the presentation of the results of the surveys. Some of the items on the survey were subjective such as "I feel economically secure now" while others were more objective such as "my current income is approximately..." As a standard procedure of this research, students were encouraged to be honest and were allowed to remain anonymous if so desired.

1. Items and Norms

Three hundred and forty-six (346) students were administered the "Resource Income Survey" questionnaire and answer sheets (see appendix) along with the REVIR IV test. The norms indicate that most of the items fall midscale and share a homogeneity of variance.

<u>Items</u>	<u>Resource</u>	<u>$\bar{X}$</u>	<u>S.D.</u>
1. I often received a great deal of warmth and affection when I was a child - (by childhood I mean the years up to about 15-16).	LV	6.2	2.1
2. I often receive a great deal of warmth and affection now.	LV	6.3	2.1
3. I often felt important and respected when I was a child.	ST	5.5	2.1
4. I often feel important and respected now.	ST	6.5	1.8
5. I often received a lot of intellectual stimulation as a child	IN	6.1	2.1
6. I receive a lot of intellectual stimulation now.	IN	7.2	1.6
7. I (and my family) felt economically secure when I was a child	MN	5.8	2.5
8. I feel economically secure now.	MN	5.8	2.2
9. My family's income during most of my childhood was about: (per year)	MN income	5.0	2.4
(1) under \$1,000	(6) \$10,000		
(2) \$2,000	(7) \$12,000		
(3) \$4,000	(8) \$14,000		
(4) \$6,000	(9) \$16,000 &		
(5) \$8,000	over		

LV
 ST
 IN
 MN
 Financial Security
 MN
 income

10. My current income is approximately: (include income of spouse or parents if relevant)

(1) under \$1,000	(6) \$12-15,000	MN income	5.7	2.1
(2) \$1-3,000	(7) \$15-18,000			
(3) \$3-6,000	(8) \$18-21,000			
(4) \$6-9,000	(9) over \$21,000			
(5) \$9-12,000				

11. I received a lot of toys, fashionable clothes, and material goods when I was a child.

GD 5.3 2.4

12. I own a fashionable wardrobe and many luxuries now.

GD 5.2 2.1

13. I often received a lot of care and concern when I was a child.

SR 6.6 2.1

14. I receive a lot of help, care, and concern now.

SR 6.6 2.0

15. I never felt ashamed about sex and/or my body as a child.

SX 5.3 2.3

16. I receive a lot of sex now.

SX 4.9 2.7

17. Approximately how often on the average do you have sex? (each month)

(1) 0-1	(6) 10	SX count	3.6	2.6
(2) twice	(7) 12			
(3) 4	(8) 14			
(4) 6	(9) 15 & over			
(5) 8				

18. If you are married or living with someone with whom you have sex circle "1." If you are single, but going steadily with someone circle "2." If you are presently unattached circle "3."

2.3 .9

19. Generally how happy are you?

6.4 1.8

2. Validity and Social Approval

The items are straightforward and their face validity

are apparent. What could be in question is whether the respondents generally were honest in responding to the items. The response set, the opportunity for anonymity, and a personal appeal from the researcher to be honest all helped to promote cooperation and honesty. The items that would be most likely to evoke some defensiveness would be sex and intimacy items. These were saved for last. After the respondent was almost through the survey and had been thoughtfully committed to it, these possibly touchier items were presented. Table 11 shows the correlations of the other items with the intimacy scale (number 18), which represents a continuum of intimacy. If the subjects generally tended to answer honestly throughout the survey, then the intimacy scale would be significantly positively related to the most intimate resources of sex and love. (On the scale, "1" represents the highest level of intimacy and "3" the lowest. The signs of the correlations are reversed to facilitate understanding.) The results indicate that the respondents generally answered in a consistently honest way. The highest significant correlations were both sex items and the love item.

Another way to test the tendency to be honest is to compare the subjective and objective items for the same resource. For example, an individual was first asked a subjective question such as "I receive a lot of sex now" and

TABLE 11

CORRELATIONS BETWEEN THE AVAILABILITY OF AN
 INTIMATE OTHER (LIVING TOGETHER, GOING STEADY, OR UNATTACHED)
 AND CURRENT RESOURCE INCOMES (N=346)

<u>RESOURCE</u>	<u>r</u>	<u>p <</u>
sex (count)	.43	.001
sex	.34	.001
love	.21	.001
status	.14	.02
services	.08	n.s.
money	.08	n.s.
financial security	.04	n.s.
information	.03	n.s.
goods	-.04	n.s.

then an objective question such as "approximately how often on the average do you have sex?" These two items should be highly correlated. The correlation between the two sex items shows a significant relationship ($r = .76$, $p < .001$). The relationships between current income (number 10) and currently feeling financially secure (number 8) ($r = .37$) and currently having goods (number 17) ($r = .37$) are both highly significantly ($p < .001$). The relationships between childhood family income (number 9) and feeling economically secure in childhood (number 7) ($r = .61$) and having goods in childhood (number 11) ($r = .41$) are also highly significant ($p < .001$).

V. RESULTS

A. Resources and Happiness

1. Simple Correlations

It was hypothesized (1.0) that the current receiving of resources would be significantly related to happiness. The results support this hypothesis. The correlations between current resource income and happiness were all significant beyond the .01 level of significance.

It was also hypothesized (1.1) that the more particularistic a resource is, the higher would be the correlation between that resource and happiness. The results show support for this hypothesis (see table 12). Love, the most particularistic resource, was most highly correlated with happiness ($r = .50, p < .001$). The next most particularistic resources, services and status, had the next highest correlations with happiness ($r = .49$ and $r = .36$ respectively, both $p < .001$).

The item least related to happiness was one's current financial income (Money) with $r = .17$. The subjective feelings associated with economic security (Financial security) had a much higher correlation with happiness ($r = .32$) than did actual financial income - possibly indicating the non-economic factors behind feeling financially secure, i.e., Hypothesis 3.0.

Sex, as an intermediate resource, was significantly related to happiness, but the correlation was rather low ($r = .25$).

TABLE 12

CORRELATIONS BETWEEN RECEIVING RESOURCES
CURRENTLY WITH ONE'S GENERAL STATE OF HAPPINESS
(N = 346)

<u>ITEM #</u>	<u>RESOURCE</u>	<u>r</u>
2	Love	.50
14	Services	.49
4	Status	.36
8	Financial Security	.32
6	Information	.30
16	Sex	.25
12	Goods	.24
10	Money	.17

2. Linear Step-Wise Regression

The effects that resources have on personal happiness may, in fact, be a function of their ability to combine with the other resources. For example, feeling economically secure may allow an individual enough time and the emotional opportunity to engage in more rewarding interpersonal activities. Another example may be that much of the pleasure associated with the exchange of sex may be a function of its association with love ("making love"). After someone has love, how much do the other resources actually contribute to happiness?

A step-wise regression was performed on the data. (It starts with the best predictor, and then goes on to indicate the next best predictors in order of their additional effects upon the cumulative systematic variance.) The results shown in table 13 indicated that love accounted for about three times as much of all the systematic variance as all the other variables combined - that is, the systematic effects that all eight variables had on happiness. Love contributed 25% of the total variance, and then: services (5%), financial security (2%), and sex and information (each 1%). After these resources, status, money income, and goods added nothing measurable to personal happiness. That is, after love - which accounted for most of the effect

TABLE 13

STEP-WISE REGRESSION OF CURRENT RESOURCES
 RECEIVED AND ONE'S GENERAL STATE OF HAPPINESS
 (N =346)

<u>RESOURCE</u>	<u>MULTIPLE</u>		<u>INCREASE</u>
	<u>R</u>	<u>R²</u>	<u>IN R²</u>
Love	.50	.25	.25
Services	.56	.31	.05
Financial security	.57	.33	.02
Sex	.58	.33	.01
Information	.58	.34	.01
Status	.58	.34	.00
Money	.58	.34	.00
Goods	.58	.34	.00

the resources had on happiness - services, feeling financially secure, sex, and information seem to make minor contributions to one's quality of life; but beyond that, additional money, status, and goods have no real effect on happiness.

3. ANOV Love and Money - Main Effects

Hypothesis 1.1 was also tested by comparing mean happiness for love and money income groups. The current love and money income data were evenly divided into three groups (high, medium, and low) and a 3 X 3 (love X money) ANOV was performed on the data, with happiness as the dependent variable. (See table 1 for cell breakdowns; i.e., they are the same as those used when values were the dependent variables.) It was predicted that love, the most particularistic resource, would be linearly related to happiness; while money, the least particularistic resource, was not expected to be linearly related to happiness.

The ANOV results showed significant main effects for both love ($F = 48.72$, $df = 2/328$, $p < .00001$), and money ($F = 6.22$, $df = 2/328$, $p < .003$; see table 14). As predicted, only love showed a significant linear trend, using orthogonal components analysis ($F_{\text{linear}} = 21.10$, $df = 1/328$, $p < .001$); while money did not ($F_{\text{linear}} < 1$; see fig. 2). The graphs presented here are used to facilitate interpretation of the ANOV results. Main effects which are not

TABLE 14

ANOVA SUMMARY RESULTS OF THE EFFECTS OF
LOVE AND MONEY INCOMES UPON HAPPINESS

<u>MEANS</u>						
<u>RESOURCE</u>	<u>LO</u>	<u>MID</u>	<u>HI</u>	<u>F</u>	<u>df</u>	<u>p <</u>
Love	5.4	6.4	7.4	48.72	2/328	.00001
Money	6.1	6.3	6.8	6.22	2/328	.003
Love X Money				5.20	4/328	.0008

<u>CELL MEANS FOR INTERACTION</u>				
Love (A)				
	<u>LO</u> (1)	<u>MID</u> (2)	<u>HI</u> (3)	
	<u>LO</u> (1)	4.8	6.5	7.1
Money (B)	<u>MID</u> (2)	5.1	6.7	7.1
	<u>HI</u> (3)	6.5	6.2	7.8

<u>SIMPLE EFFECTS</u>			
<u>Source</u>	<u>F</u>	<u>df</u>	<u>p <</u>
A for B ₁	24.19	2/328	.00001
A for B ₂	20.64	2/328	.00001
A for B ₃	14.30	2/328	.00001
B for A ₁	12.27	2/328	.0002
B for A ₂	1.31	2/328	.30
B for A ₃	3.04	2/328	.05

FIG.2 THE EFFECTS OF MONEY AND LOVE UPON ONE'S GENERAL STATE OF HAPPINESS

significant are illustrated by a straight line at the grand mean.)

Love and Money Interactions

Resources should have an additive effect on the quality of life or happiness, with each resource contributing something and some resources contributing more than others. Substitution of one resource for another, in terms of satisfaction, should follow Foa's (1971; Foa & Foa, 1974) theoretical model (see fig. 1). Love and money are opposite resources; and therefore, are least substitutable for one another. It was predicted that what was lacking in love could not be made up, in terms of happiness, with any amount of money. The results of the ANOV support this prediction.

The love X money interaction was highly significant ($p < .0008$). The simple effects and cell means are presented in table 14. People in the highest financial income group, but lowest in love income, do not have a higher quality of life than those in the lowest financial income group, but with a moderate love income (both $\bar{X} = 6.5$). While having more money does not always improve the quality of life, as with people of moderate love income ($p < .30$); having more love does increase one's quality of life, regardless of financial income ($p < .00001$). Those with both a high love and a high money income have the highest

quality of life ($\bar{X}$ =7.8; see fig. 3).

B. Resources and Values; Love Poverty and Value Substitution

It was hypothesized (2.0) that economic poverty in childhood would be related to a higher value of money currently. It was also hypothesized (2.1) that love poverty in childhood would be related to a lower value of love currently.

Two other hypotheses were proposed concerning love poverty and value substitution. It was hypothesized (3.0) that love poverty in childhood would be positively related to the current valuing of money. It was also hypothesized (3.1) that current love poverty would be positively related to the current valuing of goods.

1. Values and Resource Incomes in Childhood

The 2 X 4 (love X money) ANOV results tended to support the hypotheses. The only values that were significantly related to the independent measures were the values of love and money (see tables 15 and 16).

a. Main Effects

Love income in childhood contributed more to the formation of values than did money income in childhood. One's family's money income in childhood alone was only marginally significant in relation to one's current

FIG. 3 THE EFFECTS OF MONEY AND LOVE UPON ONE'S GENERAL STATE OF HAPPINESS-INTERACTIONS

TABLE 15

ANOV SUMMARY RESULTS OF THE EFFECTS OF LOVE AND MONEY
 INCOMES IN CHILDHOOD UPON CURRENT VALUES
 (N= 346)

<u>VALUE</u>	<u>SOURCE</u>	<u>df</u>	<u>F</u>	<u>p <</u>
MN	Love	1/338	7.72	.006
	Money	3/338	2.56	.06
	Love X Money	3/338	3.16	.025
GD	Love	1/338	<1	n.s.
	Money	3/338	<1	n.s.
	Love X Money	3/338	1.94	n.s.
SR	Love	1/338	2.14	n.s.
	Money	3/338	<1	n.s.
	Love X Money	3/338	<1	n.s.
SX	Love	1/338	2.73	n.s.
	Money	3/338	1.90	n.s.
	Love X Money	3/338	<1	n.s.
LV	Love	1/338	11.48	.002
	Money	3/338	1.70	n.s.
	Love X Money	3/338	4.83	.004
ST	Love	1/338	<1	n.s.
	Money	3/338	<1	n.s.
	Love X Money	3/338	1.10	n.s.
IN	Love	1/338	<1	n.s.
	Money	3/338	<1	n.s.
	Love X Money	3/338	2.03	n.s.

TABLE 16

THE EFFECTS OF LOVE AND MONEY INCOMES IN CHILDHOOD
 UPON THE CURRENT VALUE OF MONEY - CELL MEANS AND SIMPLE EFFECTS
 (N=346)

		LOVE (A)		
		<u>low</u> (1)	<u>high</u> (2)	
MONEY INCOME (B)	<u>low</u> (1)	11.7	9.6	p < .007
	<u>lo-mid</u> (2)	9.5	9.0	n.s.
	<u>hi-mid</u> (3)	9.1	9.7	n.s.
	<u>high</u> (4)	10.8	8.5	p < .004
		p < .004	n.s.	
<u>Simple Effects</u>				
<u>Source</u>	<u>F</u>	<u>df</u>	<u>p <</u>	
A for B ₁	7.42	1/338	.007	
A for B ₂	<1	1/338	n.s.	
A for B ₃	<1	1/338	n.s.	
A for B ₄	8.92	1/338	.004	
B for A ₁	4.63	3/338	.004	
B for A ₂	1.09	3/338	n.s.	

value of money ($p < .06$). Love income in childhood alone was highly significantly related to both the current value of money ($p < .006$) and the current value of love ($p < .002$).

The value of money tends to show a deprivation effect from money income in childhood (low $\bar{X} = 10.6$, lo-mid $\bar{X} = 9.2$, hi-mid $\bar{X} = 9.4$, high $\bar{X} = 9.6$). This shows some support for Hypothesis 2.0. On the other hand, the value of love shows the opposite of what one would expect of a deprivation effect. People from high love families valued love significantly more ($\bar{X} = 11.1$, $p < .002$) than those from low love families ($\bar{X} = 9.7$). This supports Hypothesis 2.1. Deprivation of love in childhood did not increase the value of love; but rather, receiving love early in life was positively related to valuing love later on. The deprivation of love was related to the higher valuing of money (low love $\bar{X} = 10.3$, high love $\bar{X} = 9.2$). This supports Hypothesis 3.0.

b. Interaction Effects

Both the value of money ($p < .025$) and the value of love ($p < .004$) were significantly related to the interaction of love and money incomes in childhood.

(1) Value of Money - Simple Effects

Money income was a significant factor in the formation of the value of money only in the low love groups ($p < .004$). Money income had no significant effect upon

the value of money for the high love income groups; the value of money remained low for these groups. The low-middle and high-middle money income groups did not differ in their value of money.

The low money - low love group valued money significantly more ($\bar{X} = 11.7$, $p < .007$) than the low money - high love group ($\bar{X} = 8.5$; see table 16). The value of money may be a function of either deprivation or abundance of money in a love poor family. The value of money in the low love groups (B for A_1) represents a significant quadratic function ($F = 13.00$, $df = 1/338$, $p < .001$; see fig. 4).

(2) Value of Love - Simple Effects

As with the value of money, money income was a significant influence in the formation of the value of love in only the low love family ($p < .001$). For the high love income groups, the value of love remained high regardless of the individual's family's money income. The value of love was significantly lower ($p < .0002$) in the low money - low love group ($\bar{X} = 7.9$) than in the low money - high love group ($\bar{X} = 11.4$).

While the value of money was higher for the low money - low love group than for the low money - high love group, the value of love was lower for the former group and higher for the latter group. - the relationships were reversed. The lowest value of love appeared for the low

FIG. 4 THE EFFECTS OF LOVE AND MONEY INCOMES IN CHILDHOOD UPON THE VALUE OF MONEY

money - low love group (see table 17).

There was a significant difference between the high and low love groups for the high-middle income groups. The difference was not large ($F = 4.94$, $p < .03$), it was not predicted, and is most probably a chance finding. The value of love in the low love groups (B for A_1) represents a significant linear function ($F = 12.83$, $df = 1/338$, $p < .001$). That is, as money income increased in the low love families, the value of love increased. An increase in money income for low love families could bring them to a higher level of concern so that, once insecurity associated with money poverty begins to diminish, the value of love becomes increasingly important (see fig. 5). Whereas, the low money - low love income group placed a higher value on money and a lower value on love, the high money - low love income group placed high values on both money and love.

2. Values and Current Resource Incomes

The only predicted relationship for current resource incomes was that between current love income and the value of goods. Hypothesis 3.1 predicted that current love poverty would be related to a higher relative value of goods - as a compensation or substitute for love. The relationship between love income and the

TABLE 17

THE EFFECTS OF LOVE AND MONEY INCOMES IN CHILDHOOD
UPON THE CURRENT VALUE OF LOVE - CELL MEANS AND SIMPLE EFFECTS
(N=346)

		LOVE (A)		
		<u>low</u> (1)	<u>high</u> (2)	
	<u>low</u> (1)	7.9	11.4	p < .0002
MONEY INCOME (B)	<u>lo-mid</u> (2)	10.3	11.0	n.s.
	<u>hi-mid</u> (3)	9.6	11.3	p < .03
	<u>high</u> (4)	11.1	10.5	n.s.
		p < .001	n.s.	
<u>Simple Effects</u>				
<u>Source</u>	<u>F</u>	<u>df</u>	<u>p <</u>	
A for B ₁	19.65	1/338	.002	
A for B ₂	<1	1/338	n.s.	
A for B ₃	4.94	1/338	.03	
A for B ₄	<1	1/338	n.s.	
B for A ₁	5.98	3/338	.001	
B for A ₂	<1	3/338	n.s.	

FIG.5 THE EFFECTS OF LOVE AND MONEY INCOMES IN CHILDHOOD UPON THE VALUE OF LOVE

value of goods was hypothesized to be a linear one - the less love, the greater the value of goods.

The results support the hypothesis that love poverty is related to an increased value of goods ($p < .04$). The value of goods was the only dependent variable with which the independent variables had any significant relationship. The lone significant relationship was between the value of goods and love income - a love income main effect (see table 18). The value of goods was linearly related to current love income in the predicted direction ($F_{\text{linear}} = 6604.40$, $df = 1/328$, $p < .001$; $\bar{X}_{\text{low}} = 7.1$, $\bar{X}_{\text{mid}} = 5.9$, $\bar{X}_{\text{high}} = 5.4$). Current money income had no significant effect on the value of goods ($F < 1$, $\bar{X}_{\text{grand}} = 6.1$). The value of goods may be more a function of how much love an individual is currently receiving than of how much money he has to spend (see fig. 6).

Is the value of goods at all related to needing goods or being deprived of goods? According to the hunger model (Homans, 1958, 1961), the value of goods should be negatively related to how much goods the individual received recently. The value of goods was correlated with current goods income (item 12 on the "Resource Income Survey"). The results revealed a significant relationship between the value of goods and currently receiving goods ($p < .01$).

TABLE 18

ANOV SUMMARY RESULTS OF THE EFFECTS OF LOVE AND MONEY
 INCOMES CURRENTLY UPON VALUES
 (N= 346)

<u>VALUE</u>	<u>SOURCE</u>	<u>df</u>	<u>F</u>	<u>p <</u>
MN	Love	2/328	<1	n.s.
	Money	2/328	<1	n.s.
	Love X Money	4/328	<1	n.s.
GD	Love	2/328	3.44	.04
	Money	2/328	<1	n.s.
	Love X Money	4/328	1.07	n.s.
SR	Love	2/328	<1	n.s.
	Money	2/328	<1	n.s.
	Love X Money	4/328	<1	n.s.
SX	Love	2/328	2.27	n.s.
	Money	2/328	1.89	n.s.
	Love X Money	4/328	<1	n.s.
LV	Love	2/328	<1	n.s.
	Money	2/328	<1	n.s.
	Love X Money	4/328	<1	n.s.
ST	Love	2/328	<1	n.s.
	Money	2/328	<1	n.s.
	Love X Money	4/328	<1	n.s.
IN	Love	2/328	1.90	n.s.
	Money	2/328	<1	n.s.
	Love X Money	4/328	<1	n.s.

FIG.6 THE EFFECTS OF CURRENT LOVE AND MONEY INCOMES UPON THE VALUE OF GOODS

But the result was in the opposite direction than what a deprivation effect would predict. The value of goods was positively related to having received goods recently ($r = .15$). It appears that the value of goods is less a function of financial income or the deprivation of goods, and more a function of love poverty.

VI. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS, AND CONCLUSIONS

A. Resources and Happiness

Hypothesis 1.0 was supported by the data. The receiving of resources currently was significantly related to one's general state of happiness. These results have been interpreted so that the receiving of resources would lead to happiness. An alternate interpretation - in the opposite direction (i.e., that being happy leads one to receive more resources, or that being happy leads one to believe he is receiving more resources - a halo effect) - is unlikely. If the latter interpretation were correct, then Hypothesis 1.1 could not be true. A "halo effect" interpretation of the data would have predicted that all of the resources would be equally related to happiness, but there were predictable differential relationships between resource incomes and happiness. Therefore, a "halo effect" interpretation would be incorrect.

Hypothesis 1.1 tended to be supported by the data. Love, services, and status were most related to happiness, while financial income was least related to happiness. Resource particularism appeared to be an important qualifying factor in the relationships between resource acquisition and happiness. A step-wise regression indicated that love income accounts for most of the systematic variance that all of the measured resources could contribute

to happiness.

The ANOV love X money interactions illustrated that a quantitative increase in a dissimilar resource can not "make up for" or compensate for the lack of or a deficiency in another resource - due to their basic qualitative differences. If as indicated by the results, a deficiency in love leads to a higher valuing of money, and according to the ANOV interaction results, the acquisition of money does not adequately compensate for the deficiency in love, then this value system may be called "maladaptive." A maladaptive value system does not fulfill the individual's actual needs or deficiencies, and limits the individual's potential level of happiness or quality of life.

B. Resources and Values; Love Poverty
and Value Substitution

Hypothesis 2.0 tended to be supported by the data. People tended to value money more when they came from extreme poverty backgrounds. However, the predicted deprivation effect did not hold true for the low-middle, high-middle, and high income groups. Money income of one's family of origin was more related to one's value of money currently if love had also been scarce in childhood.

Both a deprivation of money and an abundance of money in a love poor family was related to a higher value

of money. This result may be interpreted, post-hoc, as showing support for Hypothesis 3.0. It suggests that childhood love poverty is a better predictor of the current value of money than is childhood economic poverty.

Hypothesis 2.1 was supported by the data. Love poverty in childhood was related to a lower value of love currently. Students from the high love income families were not significantly affected by financial income when it came to their value of love - the value of love remained high. (The same was true for the value of money - in the opposite direction. Students from high love groups were not significantly affected by financial income with regard to their value of money - it remained low.)

It appeared that an increase in financial income in the low love groups was related to an increased value of love. It may be that only after the individual finds some financial security, can he begin to deal with more subtle needs - developing from a more concrete economic level of concern to a more feeling interpersonal level of concern.

Hypothesis 3.0 was supported by the data. Students from low love families significantly valued money more than students from high love income families. This relationship seemed particularly pointed when money was very scarce or very abundant. When both love and money

were deficient, there appeared to be an increased valuing of money and a decreased valuing of love. It is likely, that in this culture of poverty, people become more concerned with the pressures of financial survival and may tend to view others as competitors rather than as reliable sources of warmth and affection (Harrington, 1962; Lewis, 1966; Moynihan, 1966, 1967; Rainwater, 1972). Yet students from an affluent but love poor family may learn to place a high value on money as a function of its possible compensatory value or as a means of security or an indication of personal worth.

Hypothesis 3.1 was supported by the data. The current deprivation of love was related to a higher value of goods (materialism). People who seek goods as a function of needing love are seeking a resource unlikely to fulfill their need for love and significantly improve the quality of their lives. The valuing of goods is most likely to perpetuate their love poverty, as love and goods were negatively related. This negative relationship between the value of goods and the value of love was the highest correlation among all of the REVIR test values. (The next highest correlation was a significant negative relationship between the value of love and the value of money).

It is unlikely that a person with a life style oriented towards seeking goods, out of love poverty, will satisfy his real needs - as indicated by the study on values and volunteering for encounter workshops. Individuals who placed a relatively high value on money and/or goods tended to avoid situations which were likely to be intimate.

Current love poverty does not significantly affect the formation of the value of love, but may affect the value of goods. Valuing goods may, in turn, help to continue one's love poverty. (The relationship between current love poverty and the value of goods is more difficult to interpret than those between values and childhood influences. Since current love poverty and the current value of goods exist at the same point in time, it is more difficult to say which leads to which. That is, does love poverty lead to the valuing of goods, or does the valuing of goods lead to love poverty? Cause and effect conclusions cannot be made from correlations, although correlations can show support for a priori hypotheses. However, this relationship will be considered bi-directional. In other words, love poverty may lead to materialism and being materialistic may perpetuate one's love poverty.)

In a love poor affluent society with the economic means to buy almost anything; inflation, pollution, and energy shortages may result. Economic problems such as

these are not completely attributable to love poverty, but love poverty may be a contributing factor (Foa, 1971). A love hungry society that keeps consuming goods as a function of their love needs may significantly contribute to economic as well as psychological maladjustment. An individual, as well as an entire culture, may develop values that are unrelated to fulfilling actual deficits, that perpetuate those deficits, and that are based on seeking resources least related to happiness.

Charles Reich (1970) discusses in the Greening of America the evolution of values in terms of levels of consciousness:

In place of the world seen as a jungle, with every man for himself (Consciousness I) or the world seen as a meritocracy leading to a great corporate hierarchy of rigidly drawn relations and manoeuvres for position (Consciousness II), ...Consciousness III considers genuine relationships with others, friendship, companionship, love, the human community, to be among the highest values of life. (pp. 243-245)

Here the changes of goals that is so basic to Consciousness III assumes its full significance. The central point is easy to say but very hard for an older person really to grasp, so deeply does it go against the grain of Consciousness I and II. It is that the goals of status, a position in the hierarchy, security, money, possessions, power, respect, and honor are not merely wrong, they are unreal. A person whose life is one long ego trip or power trip has not merely chosen one kind of satisfaction in preference to others; he has chosen goals that have nor real relationship to personal growth, satisfaction, or happiness. (p. 257)

The theoretical implications of these hypotheses are relevant to qualifying Foa's (1971; Foa & Foa, 1974) proximity hypothesis, and the assumptions concerning the relationship of needs and values. Foa's proximity hypothesis may apply to predicting satisfaction when one resource is substituted for another, but it does not predict what resource an individual will seek when he has experienced a long-term deficiency. When that resource is love, a distal hypothesis appears to be a more accurate predictor of the substitution that may occur. The relationship between needs and values, when they are not used interchangeably, is often assumed to be a direct need-to-value relationship. However, this research shows there is an important distinction to be made. Values appear to be highly related to behavior and may not function to fulfill needs, but may, in fact, serve to maladaptively perpetuate the needs. The hunger model of motivation must be qualified by specifying the duration of an exchange and by the particular resource being exchanged. Foa's resource differentiation appears to serve a useful function when making predictions concerning the formation of values and resource reward potential. Love was found to be most related to the formation of an enduring system of values and to one's general state of happiness. It appears to be the most important resource with respect to its effects on

human behavior.

Further research is suggested that would involve replicating these results with groups known to possess various levels of the resources, and to compare their values as measured by the REVIR test. Since these results may be qualified by the particular sample used in this research, it should be replicated using other populations. In addition, a values clarification technique could be developed whereby individuals may become more aware of their current needs and values. This form of education may help individuals to re-evaluate their life styles and value priorities so that they may be able to seek a higher quality of life. Value changes on a cultural level may become an important factor in dealing with ecological and economic problems of a materialistic society.

VII. APPENDIX

THE REVIR SURVEY V

I. Wish

If I had my choice between two wishes, I would prefer...

1. (a) to have financial security
(b) to have great knowledge and wisdom
2. (a) to have financial security
(b) to be respected by people I admire
3. (a) to have a life of wealth and luxury
(b) to have great knowledge and wisdom
4. (a) to have financial security
(b) to always have a great many close friends
5. (a) to have a life of wealth and luxury
(b) to be respected by people I admire
6. (a) to always have the availability of helpful people
(b) to have great knowledge and wisdom
7. (a) to have financial security
(b) to have a fulfilling sex life
8. (a) to have a life of wealth and luxury
(b) to have a fulfilling sex life
9. (a) to always have the availability of helpful people
(b) to always have a great many close friends
10. (a) to always have the availability of helpful people
(b) to be respected by people I admire
11. (a) to have a fulfilling sex life
(b) to have great knowledge and wisdom
12. (a) to always have a great many close friends
(b) to have great knowledge and wisdom
13. (a) to have a fulfilling sex life
(b) to be respected by people I admire
14. (a) to have financial security
(b) to always have the availability of helpful people
15. (a) to have financial security
(b) to have a life of wealth and luxury

16. (a) to have a life of wealth and luxury
(b) to always have the availability of helpful people
17. (a) to always have the availability of helpful people
(b) to have a fulfilling sex life
18. (a) to have a fulfilling sex life
(b) to always have a great many close friends
19. (a) to always have a great many close friends
(b) to be respected by people I admire
20. (a) to be respected by people I admire
(b) to have great knowledge and wisdom
21. (a) to have a life of wealth and luxury
(b) to always have a great many close friends

II. Worker

If I had a choice between two otherwise similar jobs,
I would prefer...

22. (a) to work where I would earn an excellent income
(b) to have a position where I could enjoy luxuries and material wealth
23. (a) to have a position where I could enjoy luxuries and material wealth
(b) to have a position where I could have skillfull people to help me with my work
24. (a) to have a position where I could have skillful people to help me with my work
(b) to work where I would have the opportunity to meet sexually attractive people
25. (a) to work where I would have the opportunity to meet sexually attractive people
(b) to work where everyone would show a lot of affection for each other
26. (a) to work where everyone would show a lot of affection for each other
(b) to work where I would have a position of high respect
27. (a) to work where I would have a position of high respect
(b) to work at a job which is intellectually stimulating

28. (a) to work where I would earn an excellent income
(b) to have a position where I would have skillful people to help me with my work
29. (a) to have a position where I could enjoy luxuries and material wealth
(b) to work where I would have the opportunity to meet sexually attractive people
30. (a) to have a position where I would have skillful people to help me with my work
(b) to work where everyone would express a lot of affection for each other
31. (a) to work where I would have the opportunity to meet sexually attractive people
(b) to work where I would have a position of high respect
32. (a) to work where everyone would express a lot of affection for each other
(b) to work at a job which is intellectually stimulating
33. (a) to work where I would earn an excellent income
(b) to work where I would have the opportunity to meet sexually attractive people
34. (a) to have a position where I could enjoy luxuries and material wealth
(b) to work where everyone would express a lot of affection for each other
35. (a) to have a position where I would have skillful people to help me with my work
(b) to work where I would have a position of high respect
36. (a) to work where I would have the opportunity to meet sexually attractive people
(b) to work at a job which is intellectually stimulating
37. (a) to work where I would earn an excellent income
(b) to work where everyone would express a lot of affection for each other
38. (a) to have a position where I could enjoy luxuries and material wealth
(b) to work where I would have a position of high respect
39. (a) to have a position where I would have skillful people to help me with my work
(b) to work at a job which is intellectually stimulating

40. (a) to work where I would earn an excellent income
 (b) to work where I would have a position of high respect
41. (a) to have a position where I could enjoy luxuries and material wealth
 (b) to work at a job which is intellectually stimulating
42. (a) to work where I would earn an excellent income
 (b) to work at a job which is intellectually stimulating

III. Spouse

If I had my choice between two otherwise similar people, I would prefer to marry...

43. (a) someone who would make me feel important
 (b) someone very intelligent
44. (a) someone extremely affectionate
 (b) someone who would make me feel important
45. (a) someone for whom I would feel sexual attraction
 (b) someone extremely affectionate
46. (a) someone helpful to have around
 (b) someone for whom I would feel sexual attraction
47. (a) someone with whom I could share a life of wealth and luxury
 (b) someone helpful to have around
48. (a) someone who could contribute to the financial security of the family
 (b) someone with whom I could share a life of wealth and luxury
49. (a) someone extremely affectionate
 (b) someone very intelligent
50. (a) some one for whom I would feel sexual attraction
 (b) someone who would make me feel important
51. (a) someone helpful to have around
 (b) someone extremely affectionate
52. (a) someone with whom I could share a life of wealth and luxury
 (b) someone for who I would feel sexual attraction
53. (a) someone who could contribute to the financial security of the family
 (b) someone helpful to have around

54. (a) someone who could contribute to the financial security of the family
(b) someone for whom I would feel sexual attraction
55. (a) someone with whom I could share a life of wealth and luxury
(b) someone extremely affectionate
56. (a) someone helpful to have around
(b) someone who would make me feel important
57. (a) someone for whom I would feel sexual attraction
(b) someone very intelligent
58. (a) someone helpful to have around
(b) someone very intelligent
59. (a) someone with whom I could share a life of wealth and luxury
(b) someone who would make me feel important
60. (a) someone who could contribute to the financial security of the family
(b) someone extremely affectionate
61. (a) someone who could contribute to the financial security of the family
(b) someone who would make me feel important
62. (a) someone with whom I could share a life of wealth and luxury
(b) someone very intelligent
63. (a) someone who could contribute to the financial security of the family
(b) someone very intelligent

REVIR ANSWER SHEET

Name _____ Sex _____ Age _____ I.D. _____

Instructions: This is a scale of personal values, so there are no right or wrong answers. Place an "X" over the letter appropriate to your hypothetical choice. Each value is compared with every other value in three areas. Try to be as honest with yourself as possible, in order to obtain the most valid results.

I. WISH	II. WORKER			III. SPOUSE			IV. TOTAL		
	MN	GD	SR	MN	GD	SR	MN	GD	SR
1. a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2. a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3. -	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4. a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5. -	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6. -	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7. a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
8. -	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
9. -	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
10. -	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
11. -	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
12. -	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
13. -	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
14. a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
15. a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
16. -	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
17. -	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
18. -	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
19. -	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
20. -	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
21. -	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	MN	GD	SR	MN	GD	SR	MN	GD	SR

total

REVIR SCORING SHEET

Name _____ Sex _____ Age _____ I.D. _____

Instructions: Add up the X's in each column, i.e. MN, GD, SR, SX, LV, ST, and IN. Place the total number of X's at the bottom of each column. Do this for each of the three areas. Place all the totals in table #1, and obtain an overall total. Rank the relative exchange values of the interpersonal resources in table #2, from the most preferred to the least preferred, with the number of times the resource was preferred.

TABLE # 1

RESOURCE

AREA	MN	GD	SR	SX	LV	ST	IN	SUM
I. WISH	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	= 21
II. WORKER	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	= 21
III. SPOUSE	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	= 21
OVER-ALL TOTAL	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	= 63

TABLE # 2

RESOURCE PRIORITIES	NO. OF TIMES PREFERRED (0-18)	PERCENTILE
1. _____	_____	_____
2. _____	_____	_____
3. _____	_____	_____
4. _____	_____	_____
5. _____	_____	_____
6. _____	_____	_____
7. _____	_____	_____

REVIR SCORING SHEET

Name _____ Sex _____ Age _____ I.D. _____

Instructions: Add up the X's in each column, i.e. MN, GD, SR, SX, LV, ST, and IN. Place the total number of X's at the bottom of each column. Do this for each of the three areas. Place all the totals in table #1, and obtain an overall total. Rank the relative exchange values of the interpersonal resources in table #2, from the most preferred to the least preferred, with the number of times the resource was preferred.

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AREA	MN	GD	SR	SX	LV	ST	IN	SUM
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II. WORKER	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	= 21
III. SPOUSE	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	= 21
OVER-ALL TOTAL	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	= 63

TABLE # 2

RESOURCE PRIORITIES	NO. OF TIMES PREFERRED (0-18)	PERCENTILE
1. _____	_____	_____
2. _____	_____	_____
3. _____	_____	_____
4. _____	_____	_____
5. _____	_____	_____
6. _____	_____	_____
7. _____	_____	_____

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